

Recommendation for innovation governance models supporting energy efficient buildings

Deliverable 4.3 of the UMBRELLA FP7 project
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Recommendation for innovation governance models supporting energy efficient buildings

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About UMBRELLA

UMBRELLA (Business Model Innovation for High Performance Buildings Supported by Whole Life Optimisation) is a 7th Framework Programme funded SME targeted collaborative project (Grant Agreement No. 314343), which was developed to address Work Programme EeB.NMP.2012-3, Development and validation of new 'processes and business models' for the next generation of performance based energy-efficient buildings integrating new services.

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Summary of Recommendations

- Recommendation 1: Policies should aim to develop new market opportunities not attempt to stimulate demand for particular technologies.*
- Recommendation 2: Alterations to innovation systems conditions (rules) should be done on a case-by-case basis with specific objectives in mind.*
- Recommendation 3: A multi-perspective view should be taken to while improving innovation governance.*
- Recommendation 4: The concept of innovation needs to be reframed in recognition that not all innovation is technological.*
- Recommendation 5: Industry led partnerships should complement but not replace stakeholder engagement in the policy making process.*
- Recommendation 6: Greater efforts need to be made to include the views of smaller companies and non-governmental organisations in policy development.*
- Recommendation 7: Support project-based knowledge capture initiatives and develop inter-firm knowledge exchanges for energy efficiency building activity.*
- Recommendation 8: Review education and training of building professional for applicability to an enhanced focus on energy efficiency retrofits.*
- Recommendation 9: Facilitate and promote the development of financial approaches that decouple project funding from owners' ability to get credit.*
- Recommendation 10: Optimise policy mix to encourage building energy front-runners as well as laggards.*
- Recommendation 11: Review of existing policies for coherence.*
- Recommendation 12: Review of existing policy instruments for applicability to current objectives.*

1 Introduction

UMBRELLA (Business Model Innovation for High Performance Buildings Supported by Whole Life Optimisation) is a 7th Framework Programme funded SME targeted collaborative project (Grant Agreement No. 314343), which was developed to address Work Programme EeB.NMP.2012-3, Development and validation of new 'processes and business models' for the next generation of performance based energy-efficient buildings integrating new services.

Recognising the need for decision-support tools and for methods for the implementation and incentivisation of building energy efficiency solutions, the project aims to develop a web-based decision support application. This web application will provide users with common independent evaluation tools built around new and adaptable business models. The project is centred on the creation of these new innovative business models, which will be tailored to various different stakeholders (*e.g.*, owners, occupants, management companies, public authorities, *etc.*), building types, climate and policies.

An important component of facilitating the development and encouraging the adoption of these novel business models is the nature of the multi-level policy frameworks supporting innovation. This report considers the policy context for innovation in energy efficiency building projects within the regions of the UMBRELLA flagship projects, and makes recommendations for strengthening innovation governance.

Purpose

This report has been prepared in the context of Task 4.3 of the UMBRELLA project, entitled: *Recommendation for strong innovation governance and supporting policies*. The objective of the task is to use the:

“in-depth understanding of the value chain for innovative EeBs integrating new services ... to assess the existing policy frameworks supporting innovation and energy efficient buildings in the regions of the flagship projects” and to make recommendations for “improving the multi-level (local, regional, national and/or EU) innovation governance and make it a powerful support to innovative EeB projects”.

2 Background and Approach

2.1 Energy efficient buildings

2.1.1 Introduction

The construction and real estate sectors represent essential focal points for environmental sustainability initiatives due to the share of worldwide energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with the built environment. Energy efficiency in construction has become a key target in efforts to lower societal energy use (Morrissey *et al.* 2014). The retrofit of existing building represents an important and growing proportion of construction activity (Dunphy *et al.* 2013) and a ‘low hanging fruit’ of energy and emissions reduction in cost and implementation terms (Kneifel 2010).

However, as Morrissey *et al.* (2014) note, building energy efficiency activity is still only a fraction of the wider construction industry. Many barriers exist to the expansion of the sector, including perceptions of risk, information gaps, the effects of lock-in, the inertia of current practices and attitudes, split incentives and market capacity. The implementation and enforcement of an optimal mix of policies could result in reductions of approximately 30% of energy consumption at a net benefit to society (IPCC 2007; Ürge-Vorsatz & Novikova 2008). Compared to baseline projections, such estimates represent a reduction of approximately 45 EJ for buildings by 2020 (IPCC 2007). Although this potential for reducing energy consumption in the built environment has been known for decades, many of these energy efficiency possibilities have not been realised. There are certain characteristics of markets, technologies and end-users, which make rational, energy-saving choices in building design, construction, and operation, as well as in the purchase and use of appliances, surprisingly difficult.

2.1.2 Potential for energy efficiency projects

Energy efficient building projects present a significant economic opportunity. The construction, renovation and maintenance of buildings contribute between 10-40% of countries’ Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and represents, on a global average, 10% of country-level employment (UNEP SBCI, 2009). As the level of energy efficient building projects rises, new employment and business opportunities are emerging. In the U.S., a study by the Pew Charitable Trusts (2009) found that jobs in the ‘clean’ energy economy grew by over 9% between 1997 and 2007, faster than overall labour market growth. Sanchez & Poschen (2009) report on the creation of hundreds of thousands of new so-called ‘green

collar' jobs (Miranda *et al.* 2011: 56) in renewable energy production in China and Spain, in energy efficiency programs for buildings in Germany and France, and in the bio-energy and recycling sectors.

There is substantial potential for decreasing energy and energy related emissions from the built environment. Buildings are responsible for more than 40% of global energy used, and as much as one-third of global greenhouse gas emissions, both in developed and developing countries. In absolute terms, the Fifth Assessment Report of the IPCC¹ estimated building-related GHG emissions to be around 9.18 GtCO₂-eq in 2010 representing a more than doubling since 1970 (Lucon *et al.* 2014). In addition to the substantial amounts of carbon dioxide emissions, including through the use of electricity in buildings, the built environment is responsible for significant non-CO₂ GHG emissions such as halocarbons, CFCs, and HCFCs, due to their application in cooling, refrigeration, and in the case of halocarbons, as insulation materials. In most countries the residential building sector accounts for the major share of total primary energy consumption. The energy consumption in non-residential buildings such as offices, public buildings and hospitals is also significant and growing. China for example is expected to add the equivalent of twice the current US stock of office buildings by 2020 (WBSCD 2009).

These prospects for reduced energy consumption and GHG emissions avoidance are particularly evident with respect to electricity. Traditionally, it has been considered that the largest proportion (by a large margin) of energy consumption is associated with a building's operational phase, much of it in the form of electricity generated from the combustion of fossil fuels – a major source of GHG emissions. At the global level, it has been estimated that direct combustion of energy from fossil fuels in buildings released approximately 3 GtCO₂-eq in 2004, compared with 8.6 GtCO₂-eq per year from all energy end users (Ürge-Vorsatz *et al.* 2007). Similarly, the Carbon Monitoring For Action (CARMA) database of the GHG emissions of more than 50,000 power plants and 4,000 power companies in every country suggests that power generation using fossil fuels accounts for 40% of all GHG emissions in the United States and about one-quarter of global emissions (UNEP SBCI 2009).

Consequently, governments have, heretofore, tended to concentrate on the operational phase of buildings in their efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with

¹ Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

buildings including, *e.g.*, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EU 2010); increasingly more stringent national building codes; moves to implement green public procurement in respect of buildings (European Commission 2014); support for innovative financial products such as: preferential green loans (Geller et al. 2006; Sweatman & Managan 2010), UK Green Deal (DECC 2010), and the Property Assessed Clean Energy (PACE) initiatives in the USA (Ya He 2012). Life cycle studies have suggested that up to 80% of greenhouse gas emissions occur during the operational phase (Wallhagen *et al.* 2011) – as a result of energy consumed through applications such as: space heating, ventilation and air conditioning; water heating; lighting; entertainment; and telecommunications.

However the energy and GHG emissions savings potential of buildings is about more than their use phase. As building stock becomes less energy intensive in operation, through more efficient designs of new builds and upgrading of existing buildings, the relative significance of GHG emissions from the non-operational phases of a building’s lifecycle will increase. Dunphy & Henry (2012; see also Dunphy & Morrissey 2015) disaggregate lifecycle GHG emissions associated with buildings into six components as illustrated in Figure 1 below: G_{α} - emissions associated with the construction project management activities involved in delivering the building; G_{μ} - emissions arising from the various processes in the manufacture and supply of materials and products for the building; G_{ζ} - emissions arising from the construction and commissioning activities; G_{ρ} - emissions arising from the materials, goods and activities that go into the maintenance and renovation; G_{ω} - net emissions resulting from the end-of-life activities (Dunphy & Morrissey 2015; Dunphy & Henry 2012).

Figure 1: Constituents of a building’s lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions (adapted from Dunphy & Morrissey 2015; Dunphy & Henry 2012)

It can be seen from Figure 1, that in the context of reducing GHG emissions from the built environment, as the G_{θ} component reduces, it becomes increasingly important that building energy efficiency projects take a lifecycle perspective and address the G_E components. Accordingly the importance of taking a life cycle perspective is being recognised in the literature (Sturgis & Roberts 2010; Ayaz & Yang 2009) and significant reports such as the IPCC fifth assessment report (Lucon *et al.* 2014).

There is a wide range of solutions, which could significantly reduce CO₂ emissions from new and existing buildings, specifically with respect to the energy efficiency of the buildings themselves and of energy technologies applied within buildings. As energy efficiency solutions and renewable energy technologies become more affordable and flexible, they are increasingly applied in both new builds and retrofitting projects. UNEP SBCI (2009) for example note the following examples of approaches combining design and technology for low carbon buildings:

1. Passive houses, which use innovative design, site selection, orientation, significant insulation and top class craftsmanship to maintain a comfortable interior climate without active heating and cooling systems. Residual energy requirements may be sourced from conventional sources or completely covered using renewable energy sources;
2. Zero-energy buildings, where energy provided by on-site renewable energy sources, is designed to be equal to the energy used by the building. While energy can be stored on site (batteries or thermal storage) such are usually connected to the electricity grid, in order to cope with possible fluctuations in demand, especially as some buildings will produce more energy in the summer and use more in the winter;
3. Energy-plus buildings – buildings that produce more energy than they consume. This is typically measure over a year and like zero-energy buildings energy storage and grid connectively are typically considered important aspects of such designs.

Despite a variety of policy initiatives in different countries, the adoption level of many promising technologies for increasing the energy efficiency and reducing the GHG intensity of buildings is low. Furthermore, Faber and Hoppe (2013) proffer that this is not likely to increase in the near future. This creates somewhat of a puzzle with high economic and technological potential on the one hand, and low adoption levels of measures in the building sector on the other hand. It would appear that there is a need for a more supportive policy context and improvements in innovation governance models to increase innovation in

energy efficient building projects – both qualitatively and quantitatively.

2.2 Innovation

2.2.1 Defining innovation

The concept of innovation may be defined as the act of making ‘changes in something established, especially by introducing new methods, ideas, or products’ (Stevenson & Lindberg 2010), implied in this description is that the changes are useful or profitable to at least some proportion of stakeholders. Humans have always tended to seek new ways to do things and make things – the introduction of novelty into a steady state system is crucial for development and growth (Fagerberg 2003; Segarra-Blasco *et al.* 2008). Redmond (2003) posits that human behaviour is principally directed by habit and that habitual behaviour can sometimes last for (relatively) long periods of status quo and inertia, occasionally punctuated by intermittent innovation. The novelty of each innovation eventually wears off and is followed by a new set of habits, rigidities, and ceremonial behaviours – until the next innovation comes along to alter the steady state, and the cycle begins again. Of course, it cannot be assumed that all innovation is inherently positive for society just because there is a market for it. Johnson and Kwak (2012) remind us of the innovations in the financial sector during the recent boom cycle, and how there was a market (but not necessarily a true market) for new houses, but the bust cycle now shows us that the building of those houses was a ‘*destructive use of capital*’.

Imitation can also be a form of innovation, particularly where it introduces an innovation into a new context or improves on, or refines, the original innovation. Quoting Rogers (2003), Tiwari and Buse (2007) state that innovation is an idea, practice or object that is perceived as new, though the newness may not necessarily involve new knowledge, it could be the advancement or modification of existing knowledge. Historically, new was not always seen to be better or more prestigious, but according to Redmond (2003) the mass merchandising, communication, advertising and marketing of the 20th century, has equated new with better and consumers now associate new with better lifestyles and social status. What is new and to whom it is new is often also a cultural issue as well as a historical one.

Although innovation occurs in all aspects of life, including social (Mulgan *et al.* 2007), governance (Fisman & Werker 2011), creative arts (Castañer & Campos 2002) and agriculture (Diederer *et al.* 2003), it is probably most widely recognised and understood in

the context of new technologies. Fagerberg (2003), taking a somewhat business centric view, distinguishes innovation from invention describing invention as the first occurrence of a new idea for a product or a process, whereas innovation is the first commercialisation of an idea. Sometimes the two are closely linked, but more often there is a time lag between them. Tiwari and Buse (2007) describe three phases in the innovation process, namely: conception; implementation; and marketing, as indicated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Three Phases of a Simplified Innovation Process (after Tiwari & Buse 2007)

According to Abernathy and Clark (1985) while some innovations do refine and improve, there are others that disrupt, destroy and make obsolete established competence, and these are referred to in Schumpeter’s theories as “creative destruction”. Schumpeter outlined five types of innovation: new products, new methods of production, new sources of supply, exploitation of new markets, and new ways to organise business (Fagerberg 2003), while Abernathy and Clark (1985) describe four in their transience mapping for innovation, *viz.*:

1. Architectural innovation refers to that which lays down the architecture of the industry, the broad framework in which the competition will occur and develop, and it demands attention to the management of creativity and a keen insight into business risk;
2. Innovation in the market niche opens new market opportunities through the use of existing technology, and its success is highly dependent on timing and quick reaction.
3. Regular innovation is the almost invisible on-going and constant pursuit of improvement no matter how minor. It requires methodical planning and consistency as key managerial factors.
4. Revolutionary innovation is that which is most likely to fall into the category of ‘creative destruction’ when it disrupts or makes obsolete existing established technical or production competence while still being applied to the same market and customers, and is often dominated by technology.

While some innovations may ‘spring from a flash of genius’ for the most part they are the

result of a conscious purposeful search for opportunities (Drucker 1985). Drucker elaborates on this by listing four sources of opportunity within companies or industries – unexpected occurrence, incongruities, process needs, market changes – and four external sources of opportunities: social and intellectual environment; demographic changes; changes in perception. Much of the literature uses Schumpeter’s term ‘entrepreneurs’ for those innovators who capitalise on such opportunities.

2.2.2 Who are the innovators?

In network theory the triggering entity for change is usually described as the Hub or Lead organisation, the one with most power and prominence or the one with the leadership role. An ‘organisation’ as discussed here may refer to a company, a cooperative, a local authority, a government or any other group – it is not confined to commercial businesses. In individuals, the person is described as an entrepreneur.

Yong Zhao (2012), in reviewing educational performance ratings of different countries, observes that rote learning and pressure to conform pose a risk to the creativity and non-conformity necessary for innovation which is consequently being stifled and squeezed out of the system. There appears therefore to be a gap between academic achievement and entrepreneurship or innovation. If the conformers and rote learners of the world are not the innovators or entrepreneurs – then who are they? Innovators are persons, or organisational units capable of merging different types of knowledge, skills, capabilities and resources to turn an invention into an innovation (Fagerberg 2003).

Within organisations, it is often employees that are the first to identify new opportunities (Hellmann & Thiele 2011). Rosenbusch, Brinckmann, and Bausch (2011) feel that although there is literature to the effect that smaller organisations are more innovative, because they are more nimble, and less hierarchical, there is also a case for bigger firms as being more innovative. They point out that because risk and possible failure is inherent in innovation, it is often the larger more experienced organisations that can better absorb the risks, failures, and uncertainty of innovation. Thomke in Chesbrough (2010) also distinguishes between failure and mistakes. Failures are a natural outcome of an experimentation process with innovation which can be quite useful for learning, whereas mistakes are the result of poorly designed experiments. Therefore if an organisation, regardless of its size, can adopt an attitude that is favourable towards business model experimentation, and overcome and learn from their failures, this may still lead to successful innovation, and viable new business

models.

While it may not be settled whether smaller or larger organisations are more innovative, size is not the only determinant. Dahlander and Gann (2010) posit that it is an organisation's openness that leads to innovation because innovation cannot occur in a vacuum – a single organisation cannot innovate in isolation. The ability to engage with different types of partners, acquire information, and incorporate external ideas and resources is crucial to stay abreast of the competition. The authors cite Chesbrough's definition of open innovation as *"a paradigm that assumes that firms can and should use external ideas as well as internal ideas, and internal and external paths to market, as firms look to advance their technology"*. Dahlander and Gann also refer to 'pitfalls of openness', which may lead to difficulties in protecting intellectual property, resources being made available for others to exploit, and consequential problems in exploiting the innovation. This can be especially true when considering niche innovation, as described earlier, because of the ease with which it can at times be copied or improved (Dahlander & Gann 2010; Abernathy & Clark 1985).

An organisation's openness is closely linked to its capacity to absorb external knowledge Fagerberg (2003). Cohen and Levinthal (1990) expand on the idea of openness identifying what they call 'absorptive capacity' as a critical ingredient of innovation, describing it as the ability to exploit external knowledge, to be receptive to new ideas, and to understand how (and when) borrowing ideas can be more advantageous than inventing. They also argue that absorptive capacity is largely a function of prior related knowledge of the organisation because prior related knowledge is required to assimilate and use new knowledge. Ahmed (1998) says it is essential that organisations create a culture and climate in which innovation can occur. In contrast to learning-by-doing, which is more of an automatic process where an organisation becomes more practiced and efficient at what they already do, the absorptive capacity acquires outside knowledge that opens the possibility of doing something different.

Confusingly (but perhaps not unsurprisingly) early adopters of new innovations (as opposed to followers, laggards, or non-adopters) are also often described as innovators, as they possess some of the same basic traits as innovators (Redmond 2003). These include venturesomeness, intelligence, ability to cope with uncertainty, and willingness to accept risk. While the early adopters are clearly crucial to the success of an innovation, it is in fact

the followers, and other later adopters who eventually complete the transformation from innovation to social acceptance. Once the adoption process is in motion the pressure to conform eventually overwhelms the laggards.

2.2.3 Context for innovation

The difference between invention and innovation is also crucial to the understanding of the culture and climate that produces innovation. If there is a long time lag between invention and innovation, this may be because some or all of the conditions for commercialisation² were lacking in the beginning (Fagerberg 2003) – or perhaps simply not recognised. There are various examples of this, for example Leonardo da Vinci designed flying machines (Moon 2007: 255-261), but his era lacked many of the required materials, production skills and power sources, which were necessary to make his ideas a reality. Computers on the other hand did not appear until many years after many of the actual components were invented – because the components were being used in completely different applications and computers were not envisaged as useful to anyone other than perhaps massive organisations. Rogers (2003: 153-155) cites the example of Xerox who developed a set of important computing inventions including: the Alto (a contender for title of world’s first PC), a graphical user interface, the mouse, local area networks and laser printing. However they failed to commercially exploit them because they did not seem to be of much value to the firm’s existing photocopier business (see Smith & Alexander 1999). The first example of da Vinci also touches on another issue, in that many innovations need the simultaneous development of complementary innovations, or infrastructure for commercialisation – for example, cars need roads, trains need tracks, electricity needs power stations, cables, and pylons, electricians and so on.

Organisations with certain characteristics are more likely to foster innovation – those with organic structures characterised by participation, informality, face-to-face communication and an emphasis on creative aims. Innovative organisations are also likely to be outward looking, flexible, non-hierarchical, and to have effective information flows both downward and upward. Bureaucratic organisations, characterised by rigid departments, hierarchies, formal reporting, long decision chains and slow decision making, written communication, and information that travels upward while directives travel downward are not conducive to

² Taken in a more general sense to mean all types of exploitation and diffusion of innovation

innovation (Ahmed 1998). In order for an organisation to be innovative, it cannot simply announce that it intends to do so – it must develop an environment where *‘people are so comfortable with innovation that they create it’*. Ahmed considers culture to be a primary determinant of innovation. While organisational climate is defined by four dimensions, namely, (1) the nature of interpersonal relationships; (2) the nature of hierarchy; (3) the nature of work; and (4) the focus of supports or rewards, organisational culture, (or culture in general) operates at a deeper level as it refers to deeply held beliefs & values. Organisational culture has two components – explicit culture, which represents the typical patterns of behaviour by the ‘people and the distinctive artefacts that they produce and live within’, while the implicit refers to the values, beliefs, norms and premises that underline and determine the patterns of behaviour; implicit culture or the value set of the individual members – the unconscious norm of action rather than being guided by ‘procedural or other control routines’. Norms that promote innovation include, but are not limited to; challenge and belief in action, freedom and risk taking dynamism and future orientation, external orientation, trust and openness, debates, leadership commitment and involvement, and awards and rewards for example. For innovation to be successful as a culture, the organisation needs to be open to risk taking, new knowledge, and the possibility of change is required (Ahmed 1998).

Innovation, however can often be ‘siloe’d’, Dougherty (1992) for example describes “thought collectives” or “thought worlds” as communities of persons engaged in a certain domain of activity who have a shared understanding about that activity, but who cannot easily share ideas with other thought worlds. The concepts of thought worlds can include defined groups such as a specific division in a company or government department as well as very loosely related groups, such as people of a certain profession, people with similar personal tastes, or of a certain age.

2.2.4 Innovation systems

Lundvall (2005) reports that the innovation system concept developed in parallel in a number of places in Europe and the US in the 1980s (*cf.* Lundvall 1985; Freeman 1982). Although Lundvall and Freeman would each suggest that the basic ideas behind the concepts

date back to Friedrich List³ in the 19th century, Godin (2010) suggests, however, this is more a case of linking similar ideas across the years, rather than a distinct research tradition arising from List's work. The concept is useful to understand the roles and interactions within the innovative process *e.g.*, producers, private and public institutions, governments, *etc.* Faber and Hoppe (2013) suggest that an “innovation system itself may be considered as a collective emergent outcome of the interaction and co-evolution of its various elements”. Furthermore they contend that innovation systems are not of necessarily fixed delineation, providing examples dealing with: national innovation systems (Lundvall 2010); regional innovation systems (Cooke et al. 1997); sectoral innovation systems (Malerba 2002; 2005), including technology-specific innovation (Hekkert et al. 2007).

Lundvall (2005) suggests that the national innovation system might be seen as an unofficial ‘Schumpeter⁴ Mark III⁵’ driver of innovation and growth – with Mark I referring to the role of individual entrepreneurs and Mark II to that of large corporations. There is growing globalisation of business and internationalisation of supply chains and innovation process on one hand and the (perhaps not unlinked) increasing importance attached to regional industrial systems⁶. Lundvall (2010: 3-4) argues that notwithstanding the challenges that these changes bring, understanding national systems of innovation remains important, particularly in “supporting and directing process of innovation and learning”.

The national state may not necessarily be the natural boundary for innovation and learning. In many countries there is substantial sharing of competencies between central government and the regions whether that is in the framework of federal (*e.g.*, Germany), quasi-federal (*e.g.*, Spain), or devolved (*e.g.*, United Kingdom) political systems. These shared competencies, including innovation policy in many cases, combined with distinctive governance structures (*e.g.*, German Länders) and/or cultural identities (*e.g.*, Scotland) make the case for considering innovation systems at a regional level in addition to the national level (Cooke et al. 1997).

Another perspective is to focus on the actors specifically impacting on a specific industry

³ List, Friedrich (1841), *Das nationale System der politischen Ökonomie*

⁴ JA Schumpeter, Austro-Hungarian economist who identified innovation as critical aspect of economic change

⁵ Mark I, II & III referring to successive iterations or versions of productions

⁶ cf. glocalisation a concept popularised by Robertson (1997), signifying the “simultaneity — the co-presence — of both universalizing and particularizing tendencies” in global interaction

sector, Malerba (2002) describes what he terms ‘sectoral system of innovation and production’ as:

“... a set of new and established products for specific uses and the set of agents carrying out market and non-market interactions for the creation, production and sale of those products. A sectoral system has a specific knowledge base, technologies, inputs and demand. Agents are individuals and organizations at various levels of aggregation. They interact through process of communication, exchange, co-operation, competition and command, and these interactions are shaped by institutions. A sectoral system undergoes processes of change and transformation through the co-evolution of its various elements”.

Following the work of Malerba⁷ on innovation regimes, Faber and Hoppe (2013) see sectoral innovation systems as ‘the collective emergent outcome of co-evolutionary interactions between the core building blocks of a system’. They describe the building blocks of the sector in terms of four main dimensions: (1) agents and networks; (2) institutions; (3) technologies; (4) market demand as illustrated in Figure 3 and discussed below.

Figure 3: Four dimensions of sectoral patterns of innovation (after Faber & Hoppe 2013)

⁷ See, for example, Malerba and Orsenigo (1993; 1997), Malerba (2005; 2002), Malerba *et al.* (2007)

1. Agents, interactions and networks: Faber and Hoppe (2013) observe that the principal agents of change in sectoral innovation are the main sectoral agents (including public and private, individual and organisational actors) that perform core innovative activities, experiments and capacity building. The role of secondary sectoral actors in providing support measures through knowledge diffusion, financial support, regulations and counselling is also noted. Within construction, the main agents of change are those actors that design, develop and build, supply goods and service, install and finally use the buildings involved. Secondary agents include government (at multiple levels: national, regional and local), banks, public agencies, research institutions, consultancies, architects and other intermediaries. These actors exhibit a web of relationships, interacting formally and informally, through processes such as communication, exchange, cooperation, competition, and command (Malerba 2004).

2. Institutional framing: all institutions exist in the context of a specific operational environment, comprising a myriad of values, routines, habits, practices, standards and laws, all of which frame perceptions and shape the actions and relations of the agents (Malerba 2002). Faber & Hoppe (2013) observe that the institutional setting is a key determinant of the characteristics of innovation in a particular industry and suggest understanding the institutional setting is of particular relevance for environmentally related innovation as such markets are, at least in the initial stage, defined (*i.e.* the rules are set) by public policy, while also stressing the role of non-regulatory institutions in providing legitimacy through an external value system.

3. Faber and Hoppe (2013) define the **Technological Regime** as describing the potential links and complementarity between technologies, involves the combination of the following four defining features:

- a) the nature and means of dissemination of the ‘knowledge base’ upon which companies’ innovative activities are based;
- b) the ‘technology opportunity’ *i.e.*, the easiness of innovating for a given investment;
- c) facilitating financial return for innovation and protection from imitation;

- d) the cumulative quantity of innovation in a country – a reflection that innovations in the future likely build upon innovative activities now.

4. Market demand: According to neoclassical economy, the role of demand in the understanding of technological change and innovation is considered a passive one. To neoclassical economists, demand stems from private preferences, which are revealed by actual consumer choices. However, in evolutionary approaches, asymmetry in information or skills, constraints in opportunity, or heterogeneity of intrinsic motivations and preferences lead to a wide variety of preferences, for both consumers and producers. This has the consequence, as Faber and Hoppe state, that there is considerable scope for the improvement of the demand side dimension in innovation system studies. This is especially the case when dealing with transitions in socio-technical systems (see Witt 2011). The four dimensions described above and illustrated in Figure 3 may be considered as subsystems of the sectoral innovation system. Barriers and triggers for innovation may exist in each of the subsystems and the interactions between these four dimensions leads to the emergence and development of new innovations (technological or otherwise) (Faber & Hoppe 2013).

2.3 Flagship Projects

2.3.1 Introduction

The four flagship projects are examples of different types of energy efficient building project, including: new build, retrofit, public sector, private, housing, commercial, *etc.* Each of the projects also represents a different lifecycle stage or hub of activity as outlined in Table 1 below and treated extensively in UMBRELLA deliverable 2.1.

Hub	Example of activity
#1 Upstream activities	Extraction of raw materials, manufacture, transport, <i>etc.</i>
#2 Initiation & viability check	Original proposal, making business case, <i>etc.</i>
#3 Design & planning	Designs, building plans, project plans, <i>etc.</i>
#4 Construction and/or installation	All site activities
#5 Operation and maintenance	Use and upkeep
#6 End of life and downstream activities	Deconstruction, reuse, recycling, disposal, <i>etc.</i>

Table 1: Hubs of Activity of construction projects (after Dunphy *et al.* 2013)

The following sections present a summary description of the flagship projects in Italy (*hub #2* initiation & viability check); Poland (*hub #3* Design & planning); Spain (*hub #4* construction / implementation); and the United Kingdom (*hub #5* operation & maintenance).

2.3.2 Public School (Italy)

The publicly owned school, located in the Piedmont Region, was built in 1965, and is in an advanced state of deterioration, with minimum maintenance activities performed in the last 10 years. The objective of the project is to increase the internal comfort while reducing the energy consumption of the building. The Municipality has a contract for the heating supply for which it paid €35k per year on average and is interested to determine the total amount of the investment required to increase the comfort of the building. The project will intervene in the generation of power, regulation and insulation.

The system enclosure has a low efficiency for the complete absence of insulation in the walls and the presence of numerous critical points: neon ceiling-lights, windows with aluminium frames without thermal break, *etc.* The biomass boiler currently installed also needs to be replaced, because of its inefficiency (it was installed 20 years ago) and because it is oversized compared to the power required under current conditions. The intervention on the vertical opaque casing includes the outer insulation of the entire envelope in order to reach a value of total transmittance of $U=0.24W/m^2K$. The transmittance value will be obtained using 14 cm thickness of XPS (extruded polystyrene foam) in addition to the adhesive layers and the finishing of the system to coat. Regarding the control system, the current regulation “area only” will be replaced with a thermostat climate control + environment with proportional controller with a bandwidth of 1°C (thermostatic valve).

2.3.3 Hotel Development (Poland)

The Polish development is located in the province of Pomerania. It consists of two main parts: a five-star hotel and residential units. The concept of the building and design process is on-going and construction is due to be completed by 2015. The main part of the hotel building consists of four aboveground levels with hotel rooms, offices, SPA, swimming pool, cinema. The high part of the hotel building consists of six aboveground levels with restaurant, conference rooms and hotel apartments. There is one underground level under the whole building. There are 170 hotel rooms and 24 hotel apartments. The total area of the hotel is approximately 12,000 m². The residential building is placed next to the hotel, it comprises four floors aboveground and one underground, with a total of 27 apartments. The total area of the residential building is approximately 3000 m².

The project will adapt solutions that improve the energy performance of the building and reduce operating costs regarding lighting, HVAC system, heating system, construction details, building materials, etc. It will introduce new sources of renewable Energy: PV and heat pumps (for the hotel: ground heat pump 170 kW and oil boiler 1100 kW; and for the housing: ground heat pump 85 kW and electrical boiler 45 kW); optimise the wall and roof thermal insulation and windows (with an U value of $U=0.26 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for the walls and $U= 1.3 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ for the windows); install LED lighting; use of rainwater; use of aerators on taps and thermostatic taps. The main objectives of the project are: the reduction of operational costs; < 7 years of Simple Pay Back Time (SPBT) of energy efficiency measures; and 12 years for PVP. The energy efficiency measures to be implemented are BMS, RES, lighting and a PV system of 38.4 kWp. It will influence both the energy efficiency and operating costs.

2.3.4 Commercial & residential development (Spain)

The development is located in Valencia city in the Valencia Autonomous Community. The development consists of three main parts: 1,400 m² of communal parking lot, shared with the neighbouring buildings; the housing part of the building with 5 flats each on the 1st, 2nd and 3rd floor and 3 flats on the 4th floor; and the commercial part of the building at ground level. The project is in the city centre of Valencia and integrated in a bigger rehabilitation project of the city. Four more buildings are included in the global project, but the works have been interrupted because of the financial crisis. The project has implemented technical solutions with high-energy performance to reduce the operating costs. The EEB measures have been: optimisation of the envelope of the building (the transmittance of the building is $U=0.505 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) to make it 40% more efficient than required by current legislation ($U=0.82\text{W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$). The windows' thermal insulation ($U=3.3\text{W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) has a 50% higher efficiency required by current legislation ($U=5.7\text{W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$). The solar heating system will provide 60% of sanitary hot water. Finally a hygro-regulated (*i.e.* moisture regulated) ventilation system is supposed to allow for a 48% energy savings compared to the current state-of-the-art solutions

2.3.5 Co-housing project (United Kingdom)

This project is a co-housing development of 25 houses located within a pre-existing large intentional community in the Moray Council area of Scotland in the United Kingdom. an intentional community is a residential community designed to have a high degree of social cohesion through shared values. The existing ecovillage consists of some 61 environmentally designed buildings, some of which are co-housing while others are self-build units. The houses were designed and built to achieve leading environmental performance standards current at their time of

construction. Electrical demand is met through wind turbines owned by the community and distributed through a private grid; surplus electricity is exported to the national grid. The four pillars of the co-housing design concept are ecological awareness, shared living, scale and setting and mixed/low cost. The key design elements are:

- 40% GGBS and recycled hard core used in any concrete;
- External walls comprised of timber, straw and lime render composite system;
- Internal walls allow for flexible spaces due to the use of a massive timber internal wall system;
- A cassette roof system with recycled cellulose insulation;
- Low energy external doors and windows ($1.2 \text{ w/m}^2\text{K}$);
- Locally produced internal doors and stairs with FSC approved timber;
- Steel profile sheet roofing with Sedum roofing (green roof) to flexi-units, common room and boiler house;
- Home-grown timber studs with 60 mm wood fibre and finished with pre-painted larch cladding walls;
- Warmcell (recycled paper) insulation;
- Electricity to be substantially supplied from community owned wind park;
- District heating system powered by a central biomass boiler;
- Opening windows and passive stack ventilation systems provide fresh air to the house. Single glazed sunspace to all dwellings capable of opening out in summer to form a balcony;
- Individual solar thermal panels to top up domestic cylinders;
- U-values to be equivalent to the requirements of AECB Silver Standard *e.g.* maximum U-value for roofs of $0.15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$;
- Construction air tightness levels of $\leq 3 \text{ m}^3 / \text{m}^2\text{h}$.

2.4 Methodological Approach

This report explores means of improving innovation governance⁸ for energy efficient building activity, within the context of the four countries, which are home to the UMBRELLA flagship projects (*i.e.*, Spain, Italy, Poland and the United Kingdom).

A five step approach is adopted for this work and detailed below:

Step 1 – firstly, the political structure and the policy and regulation context of each country is described at national, regional and as appropriate local levels. The relationship of the central government to the regions and the division of power, formal and informal is discussed.

Step 2 – policies relevant to energy efficient building were identified through a systematic process, and categorised and characterised on the basis of: energy efficiency potential; emissions reduction effectiveness; cost-effectiveness; impact on innovation; and potential for synergies.

Step 3 – next, the innovation governance systems in each of the four countries were described in terms of key actors, roles, policies, *etc.*

Step 4 – potential barriers to innovation in the context of energy efficient building projects were identified through extensive stakeholder interviews (>100 respondents), a detailed literature review, and review of policy.

Step 5 – lastly, recommendations for improving innovation governance for the building energy efficiency sector were forwarded, building on the understanding of innovation systems failures developed by Klein Woolthuis *et al.* (2005)

⁸ While it is recognised that some authors use the term ‘innovation governance’ to refer the management of innovation with private organisations, within this report the conventional meaning of referring to the public sphere is adopted.

3 Policy and regulatory context

3.1 Kingdom of Spain

3.1.1 Overview

While the Kingdom of Spain is nominally a unitary state, a leading Spanish constitution scholar, Aja (2003) observed that the features of the autonomous statutes and the way in which the constitution was employed, corresponds to the essential features of federal systems. The Spanish government is heavily decentralised into seventeen autonomous communities with different levels of devolved competences. Under the 1978 constitution, sovereignty resides in the central institutions of government; however Article Two of the constitution also recognises the right to self-government of the ‘nationalities and regions’ of which Spain is composed. The powers of each autonomous community are set out in its particular Statute of Autonomy and guaranteed by the Spanish constitution. All competences not officially assumed by the Spanish state in the constitution can be assumed by an autonomous community in its Statute of Autonomy, while all powers not so assumed remain with the state. The autonomous communities have wide powers over spending, but most taxes are levied and collected by central government and redistributed.

Energy policy is largely determined by the central government. Articles 149(1)(22) and (25) of the Spanish Constitution reserve for the state a broad jurisdiction over the energy regime. This is reinforced by the basic state legislation, which establishes the sector’s regulatory framework: the Electrical Sector Law 54/1997 and the Hydrocarbon Law 34/1998. Since these two laws are very comprehensive and wide-ranging, there is little space in practice for the autonomous regions to regulate. Building standards and energy efficiency requirements are also largely set at central government level, with the autonomous communities, including Valencia, offering a number of additional financing programmes.

Valencia is an autonomous community with nationality status. It was established by the promulgation of its first Statute of Autonomy in 1982. A new Statute of Autonomy was promulgated in 2006. With a population of 5.1 million Valencia is the fourth most populous autonomous community in Spain.

The Spanish constitution also recognises the municipalities and provinces and guarantees their autonomy. Each municipality is a corporation with an independent legal personality; they enjoy a large degree of autonomy in administering local affairs. Administrative councils

govern provinces, albeit they have limited administrative competencies.

In summary, virtually all policy relating to energy efficient buildings is set at national level, but its implementation is in the hands of the autonomous communities who have some degree of freedom in how they do this.

3.1.2 Spanish National Government

There are three ministries of particular relevance to the energy efficient building sector. The Ministry of Industry, Energy and Tourism (Ministerio de Industria, Energía y Turismo) is responsible for setting Spanish energy policy and its implementation, including the development of regulatory proposals and, among other things, approvals of tariff structures, energy product prices and network access tolls in accordance with current legislation. The Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment (Ministerio de Agricultura, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente) proposes and implements government policy in relation to climate change and environmental protection (among other things), without prejudice to the role of regional bodies which have related duties in their corresponding regions. The mission of the Ministry of Industry, Energy and Commerce (Ministerio de Industria, Energía y Turismo) is to develop competitiveness by facilitating energy security at least cost, stimulating domestic and international commerce, cutting-edge technology and communications, and supporting fair competition and research, applying the results to increase economic activity.

The main policy framework governing energy efficient buildings in Spain is provided by the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2011-20⁹, which uses packages of measures including regulation, financial incentives, training, information and inspections to:

- Improve the thermal envelop of existing buildings;
- Improve the energy efficiency of thermal installations in existing buildings;
- Improve the energy efficiency of lighting in existing buildings;
- Promote the energy renewal of existing buildings to achieve Class A or B energy ratings;
- Promote the construction of new buildings which achieve Class A or B energy ratings;

⁹ Also of relevance are the New National Energy Plan, 2008-16; and the Spanish Strategy on Climate Change and Clean Energy (2007-2012-2020), which sets out targets for reducing Greenhouse Gas emissions in line with Kyoto targets and Spain's European obligations

- Promote the construction of new buildings, which achieve nearly zero energy consumption.

Overall responsibility for the Energy Efficiency Action Plan lies with the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Tourism, operating through the Institute for Diversification and Saving of Energy (IDAE). The plan is implemented through a co-management and co-funding mechanism involving the central government and the Autonomous Communities signing collaboration agreements, which define the way in which the Autonomous Communities execute the measures contained in the plan. Funding is provided by the IDAE, with additional funding coming from the autonomous communities themselves. The Autonomous Communities managed 75% of the total budget for the previous 2005-2007 and 2008-2012 Action Plans, with the IDEA managing the remaining 25%.

The central government also provides a variety of financing programmes, which support the retrofitting of residential buildings, the use of geothermal, biomass and solar energy for water and space heating in buildings, and improved energy efficiency in existing buildings in the tourism sector.

Building regulations are set centrally, with the main legislation being the Spanish Planning and Building Decree, 1999. This has been substantially modified as a result of the partial transposition of Directive 2002/91/EC from the European Parliament and Council relative to the energy efficiency of buildings into Spanish Law through the following Royal Decrees:

- Royal Decree 314/2006, of 17 March, approving the Technical Building Code;
- Royal Decree 47/2007, of 19 January, approving the basic procedure for the energy certification of newly built buildings;
- Royal Decree 1027/2007, of 20 July, approving the Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings;
- Royal Decree concerning the energy certification of existing buildings.

3.1.3 Valencia Regional Government

The Valencian autonomous community is responsible for the implementation of the majority of regulations and programmes under the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2012-20. The agreements signed with IDAE distinguish between priority measures and additional measures. The first are implemented by all Autonomous Communities, guaranteeing uniform application of the action plans across Spain, while the second are left to the decision

of the Autonomous Communities themselves.

The Valencia Regional Government has put in place number of additional financial supports to promote savings and energy efficiency in buildings, besides national measures, including financial supports for sustainable urban development.

The Valencia Regional government also has its own Energy Action plan for 2012-20, the implementation of which is the responsibility of the Valencia Energy Agency (AVEN). The policy is based on the four principles of self-sufficiency, energy savings, technical and economic efficiency, and sustainability. As part of the plan, AVEN is implementing a number of programmes relevant to the area of energy efficient buildings:

- A plan to cut energy use in public buildings by 20% by 2016;
- Monitoring and enforcing national and EU legislation on energy efficiency in buildings
- Increasing the number of energy audits of buildings;
- Providing investment incentives for energy efficient buildings and renewable energy, using additional finance from the Valencia Regional Government and the European Investment Bank .

While policy is largely set at national level, the regional government has significant scope to influence its implementation, as well as to introduce additional measures (primarily financial incentives, information, and training) to promote energy efficient buildings. The Valencia Regional Government has made significant use of the opportunities this offers to them to take a pro-active role in shaping policy on energy efficiency in its own region.

In addition to the national policy, many autonomous communities have developed their own Energy Policies, including renewable energy targets. The autonomous communities (Regional Governments) manage almost 50% of the national budget. Therefore, they are decisive in the implementation of policy, even that which has been formulated at national level.

3.2 United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

3.2.1 Overview

Scotland is a component part of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland. The UK has traditionally been a centralised state; in recent years there has been asymmetric

devolution of power to Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland¹⁰, while the UK parliament has retained full responsibility for all issues within England. However notwithstanding this devolution, the UK – which has no written constitution – remains a unitary state and the UK parliament has the power to overrule the devolved assemblies. Under the terms of the Scotland Act 1998, which established devolution, energy policy is a matter specifically reserved to the UK parliament. On the other hand, planning is a devolved matter and the Scottish government sets building regulations. Notwithstanding, current proposals for increased devolution, the Scottish government is largely reliant on the UK exchequer for funding through a block grant system. Heretofore, policy on energy efficiency and building retrofit has therefore primarily been determined at UK level, although some additional regulatory measures and funding schemes for households have been established by the Scottish administration.

Within Scotland the administration is strongly centralised and local authorities have little impact on policy, although Moray Council, in whose jurisdiction Findhorn is located, runs a Home Energy Efficiency Programme funded by the Scottish government. Local authorities also administer the building standards and are responsible for granting permission for work to be done (Building Warrant) and a completed building to be occupied (Completion Certificate).

The division of powers between UK and Scottish governments is currently subject to renegotiation after the 2014 Scottish independence referendum, and energy policy is one area in which the Scottish government is seeking to gain additional powers.

3.2.2 UK National Government

The central UK government largely determines the policy framework for energy efficient buildings in Scotland. In 2008 the UK created the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), which has combined responsibility for policy on energy and climate change. The department's declared priorities are supporting investment in the UK's energy infrastructure, supporting consumers and keeping energy bills down, and promoting action in the EU and internationally to maintain energy security and mitigate dangerous climate

¹⁰ As provided for in UK Acts of Parliament (and an international agreement in the case of Northern Ireland), viz., Scotland: Scotland Acts 1998-2012; Wales: Government of Wales Act 1998; Northern Ireland: Good Friday Agreement 1998 and Northern Ireland Act 1998

change.

The UK is committed to the EU's targets, set out in the 'Energy Roadmap 2050' adopted by the European Commission on 15th December 2011, of reducing greenhouse gas emissions to 80-95% below 1990 levels by 2050.

Key legislation at the UK level includes:

- Energy Act (2013) – includes provisions to reform the electricity market for purposes of promoting low-carbon electricity generation, putting in place the framework to bring forward GBP 110 billion of investment in electricity infrastructure over the next decade
- Energy Act (2011) – includes a range of provisions related to energy efficiency in domestic buildings, including the Green Deal financing framework to help people make energy efficiency improvements to buildings, an Energy Company Obligation on energy suppliers to deliver energy efficiency measures to domestic energy users, and new regulations for the private rented sector.
- Climate Change Act (2008) – sets ambitious, legally-binding targets to reduce emissions and strengthens the institutional framework to achieve this
- UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2007)

Measures specifically governing energy efficient buildings include:

- Renewable Heating Incentive (RHI) (2011/2014) – Financial incentive scheme to encourage uptake of renewable heating. Mainly targeting big business and commercial users, but also applicable to domestic users and landlords
- Changes to Green Deal (2013) – grants are given to help people buying a house to which they plan to make energy efficiency improvements, alongside new incentives for private landlords.
- Feed-in Tariffs (2008) – ensures people who have invested in small-scale (less than 5MW) low-carbon electricity generation guaranteed payment from electricity providers for surplus electricity they generate and export to the grid
- Zero Carbon Homes and Building Regulation (2007) - all new homes need to be zero carbon from 2016 and all new non-domestic buildings from 2019. This will be delivered through a progressive tightening of building regulations
- Landlord's Energy Saving Allowance (2007) – offers tax relief to landlords on the cost of purchasing and installing energy-saving products
- The following standards relevant to energy efficient buildings are established at UK level:

- PAS (Publicly Available Specification) 2030 Standards – all energy efficiency measures, financed under the Green Deal, must be installed in full accordance with these standards
- Zero Carbon Homes Standards – the government is due to introduce standards to implement the Zero Carbon Homes and Building Regulation during 2014. However they will not apply to developments of under 50 new homes and will also provide loopholes for larger developers
- Microgeneration Certification Scheme – an industry-led quality insurance scheme, supported by DECC, which certifies microgeneration products used to produce electricity and heat from renewable sources

3.2.3 Scottish Government

The Scottish government has introduced several legislative and policy measures relevant to energy efficiency, largely to implement existing EU and UK policy. The Climate Change (Scotland) Act (2009) sets out the statutory framework for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in Scotland. In line with wider UK goals, the Scottish government aims to achieve an 80% reduction in Scotland's carbon emissions by 2050. Certification of the energy performance of buildings (both domestic and non-domestic) has been introduced under the Building (Scotland) Act 2003 and the Energy Performance of Buildings (Scotland) Regulations 2008. The Building (Scotland) amendment regulations, necessitated to implement the EPBD, came into effect in October 2010, and tightened standards on the energy performance of buildings. Requirements to reduce CO₂ emissions and optimise the energy performance of new buildings are included in Scottish building regulations.

A number of additional grant and support schemes for energy efficient buildings have been introduced which apply specifically to Scotland:

- Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland (HEEPS) – includes several programmes to tackle fuel poverty and improve energy efficiency in homes for people with difficulty paying their bills
- Home Energy Efficiency Learning Network – provides advice to individuals and organisations working in the housing sector
- Energy and Resource Efficiency Service – provides energy efficiency advice to businesses in Scotland

The Scottish government is also responsible for setting building standards. Measures include:

- Scottish Housing Quality Standard – the Scottish Government's principal measure of housing quality in Scotland
- Building Standards – these include energy standards, which are often reviewed (every three years since 2007). These currently vary in a number of respects from the UK building standard, including a tighter insulation standard for walls.

There are a limited number of energy efficiency schemes run by local councils, with funding from either the UK or Scottish governments:

- Green Deal Communities Scheme – as part of the Green Deal, this encourages local authorities to develop innovative area-based Green Deal Schemes.
- HEEPS area-based schemes: the Scottish government works with local authorities to help finance energy efficiency improvements for vulnerable homeowners and tenants, in order to make their homes easier and cheaper to warm

Moray Council runs a Home Energy Efficiency Programme funded by the Scottish government under the auspices of HEEPS. This focuses on providing insulation and boiler replacement to 'hard to treat' properties, and incorporates discrete projects aimed at helping older people and private tenants.

3.3 Republic of Poland

3.3.1 Overview

The Republic of Poland is a unitary state whose system of government is a constitutional parliamentary democracy. Responsibility for energy policy is heavily concentrated at national government level.

Local government is organised on municipal, district and provincial levels. Poland was highly centralised during the decades of communist power. Local government reforms in 1998 increased the role of local government, but it remains relatively weak by international standards. It is treated primarily as a service delivery unit and carries out administrative functions on behalf of central government.

Municipal governments are the only level of local government that is protected in the constitution. They are responsible for the vast majority of local government spending, and are the only tier of local government with the right to raise some (limited) taxes. Among their other roles, municipalities are responsible for local spatial planning. The competences and revenues of district and provincial administrations are more limited. However from the perspective of energy efficient buildings, these levels are perhaps more significant, since

building inspections are carried out by the district administration and regional administrations are responsible for strategic planning and local development programmes as well as providing some funding for energy efficiency measures. Jurata, where the flagship project is located, is part of the municipality of Jastarnia, in the district of Puck County, province of Pomerania.

Poland's energy intensity, while decreasing, remains nearly double the EU average. Residential energy consumption in Poland is also higher than in other countries with a similar climate. The government aims to achieve zero growth in energy demand over the medium to long-term in order to reduce energy intensity to the level of the EU-15¹¹ by 2030.

3.3.2 Polish National Government

While control over energy policy, including energy efficiency, is concentrated in central government, responsibility is fragmented, being divided between multiple departments and agencies. The Ministry of Economy is responsible for energy policy, including energy efficiency policies. The Ministry of Environment has charge of climate policy. The Housing and Urban Development Office, supervised by the Ministry of Infrastructure, is responsible for the operation of a central plank of Poland's energy efficiency policy, the Thermo-Modernisation Fund. The Ministry of Regional Development and Buildings has been responsible for the introduction of new building standards. The legislative and policy framework governing energy efficiency and renewable energy includes:

- Energy Law Act (1997) – establishes the basic regulatory framework for the energy sector
- First National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2007) – aims to achieve 9% energy savings by 2016
- Polish Energy Policy (2009) - the main priorities outlined are energy security, economic competitiveness, nuclear power, increasing environmental protection, and improving energy efficiency.
- Law on Energy Efficiency (2011) – for the first time, this law introduced a robust regulatory framework to ensure implementation of energy efficiency goals. It also introduced the White Certificate Programme (WCP), which requires companies selling electricity, heat or natural gas to have energy efficiency certificates.

¹¹ Those countries who were members of the European Union prior to the May 2004 accession of ten candidate countries.

- Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2011-2016 (adopted April 2012) – this contains planned measures for improving energy efficiency in various sectors of the economy. The proposed measures will be as far as possible be based on market mechanisms and rely minimally on the state budget.
- National Renewable Energy Action Plan (NREAP) – sets out a detailed roadmap for how Poland plans to meet its binding national target of 15% renewable energy as a share of final consumption by 2020 within the context of the EU’s climate and energy package.

Specific policy measures, which Poland has brought forward to promote energy efficiency include:

- New building standards requiring improved thermal insulation and energy performance (2008)
- Certificates for the energy performance of buildings and a mechanism for inspecting and assessing their energy efficiency (2007)
- Thermo-Modernisation Fund to promote energy efficiency investments in households, including in heating systems, and assist the penetration of energy efficient appliances
- Financial incentives to promote solar collectors in the household sector
- The Prosumer programme, which helps finance the installation of renewable energy micro-generation capacity
- The Energy Efficient House scheme, offering grants to people who build or retrofit their homes to high standards of energy efficiency
- Information dissemination and advocacy measures

3.3.3 Pomeranian Voivodeship

The Pomeranian Voivodeship is situated in the north of Poland on the Baltic sea coast, and includes 5.9% of Poland’s land area and 2.2 million people or 5.8% of the country’s population. Pomerania has adopted a Regional Strategy for Energy Development running from 2007-2025, which focuses on energy efficiency, increasing renewable energy supply, and reducing carbon emissions. The region was also one of twelve pioneer regions across Europe to participate in ENNEREG (Regions paving the way for a Sustainable Energy Europe), a project that aimed to inspire EU Regions to take up the challenges of fulfilling the EU 20-20-20 climate and energy targets. As part of the project Pomerania prepared a regional Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP).

The Pomeranian Province Development Strategy 2020 also sets specific objectives for the region in relation to improved energy efficiency, the development of distributed generation, and achieving a high penetration of renewable energy. The share of electricity produced from renewable energy sources as a percentage of total consumption in the region should reach a minimum of 15% by 2020 (compared to a 9.84% share in 2010). Unit heat consumption in residential and public utility buildings should be reduced by 20% in relation to the base value in 2010 of 230 kWh/m²/year.

Pomerania has therefore developed a body of regional policy relating to energy efficiency and renewable energy resources, including specific targets for energy efficiency in buildings. However this has taken place within the parameters of existing European and Polish legislation, as the regional administration has neither the competence nor the financial resources to go beyond these.

3.4 Italian Republic

3.4.1 Overview

The Italian Republic is a unitary parliamentary republic with a strong measure of devolved government. The state is divided into regions (regioni), provinces (province), and communes (comuni). There are fifteen ordinary regions and an additional five autonomous regions. Piedmont, where the flagship project is located, is a region with ordinary powers.

In recent years Italy has seen substantial devolution of legislative and regulatory powers to the regions. In 2001 a series of constitutional amendments created a new framework for sharing regulatory competences, including in the area of energy, between the state and the regions. The regions now have powers over any legislative area not explicitly reserved to the national parliament. The protection of the environment is listed among the exclusive competences of the state. In energy policy, on the other hand, the state and the regions have concurrent legislative powers, meaning the regions have the power to enact legislation provided it does not conflict with the policy framework established at state level. The legislative powers of both special and ordinary regions are subject to certain constitutional limitations, the most important of which is that regional legislation may not conflict with national interests. Each region contains a number of provinces, which have their own elected councils, executive committees and presidents. The commune is the smallest local government unit, and includes a popularly elected communal council, the communal

executive, and mayor. The communes have the power to levy and collect limited local taxes. Since 1990 a series of laws have given these levels of local government more autonomy.

3.4.2 Italian National Government

Central government in Italy sets the overarching legislative framework for energy policy, including in relation to energy efficient buildings. The Ministry of Economic Development is responsible for national energy policy. The Ministry of Environment and Protection of Land and Sea is responsible for co-ordinating policy on climate change and, together with the Ministry of Economic Development, for promoting and developing renewable energy and energy efficiency. Key elements of the legislative and policy framework include:

- National Energy Strategy – energy efficiency is identified as the ideal instrument for pursuing all the objectives of the policy. The strategy mandates stronger minimum standards, especially for the construction industry; an extension of the timescale for tax deductions for energy efficient renovations; the introduction of direct incentives for retrofitting public buildings; and greater use of white certificates
- Decree of 15th March 2012 of the Ministry of Economic Development – for each Italian Region, this sets targets of gross final energy consumption and the proportion of electricity and heat to be produced from renewable sources up to 2020.
- Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2011) – updates measures to improve energy efficiency, including the introduction of minimum standards for new and renovated buildings in the residential and tertiary sectors.
- National Renewable Energy Action Plan (2010) – sets a target of supplying 26.4% of electricity from renewable sources by 2020
- Building Standards – strictly speaking there is no unified national system of building regulations in Italy, since these are the responsibility of the communes. However both the state and individual regions set guidelines to which communal building codes must adhere. A series of measures (Decree Law 115/2008, the Ministerial Decree 26 June 2009 and Decree Law 28/2011) have been introduced by the central government, which set minimum efficiency requirements for new buildings and for existing buildings undergoing major renovation. All buildings bought, sold or leased, whether residential or commercial, require an energy performance certificate.

Some of the specific measures brought forward under this policy framework include:

- 55% Tax Rebate Scheme – the 55% tax rebate scheme provides tax credits to householders for energy retrofits.
- Energy Efficiency Certificates (White Certificates) – each electricity and gas distributor with more than 50,000 final users has to achieve a target of energy

savings, certified by White Certificates.

- Renewable Energy for Heating and Cooling Support Scheme (Conto Termico) – this scheme provides support for small-scale projects involving energy efficiency improvement and the production of thermal energy from renewables.
- Kyoto Fund - SMEs, PAs or individuals can benefit from a 0.5% interest rate on loans to facilitate energy efficiency projects.
- Residential Solar PV – this is incentivised through tax rebates and net metering laws.
- Leadership – all new public buildings and buildings undergoing major refurbishment must take the use of integrated renewable energy systems into consideration

In summary, the Italian national government has the strongest influence on policy regarding energy efficient buildings. However both regions and communes have a significant role in implementation, and can develop or alter policy within the legislative framework established by the state. This is particularly the case with building standards.

3.4.3 Piedmont Region

Situated in the far northwest of Italy, Piedmont has a population of 4.6 million and is one of the largest Italian regional economies. The Regional Law n. 13/2007 promotes the improvement of energy performance in both existing buildings and new constructions. It seeks to facilitate the development, enhancement and integration of renewable sources and energy diversification, while taking into account local climatic conditions. The law details the application of minimum standards for energy performance to both new buildings and existing buildings undergoing renovation. It also outlines criteria for the energy certification of buildings; mandates regular inspection of heating and air conditioning systems; sets criteria for accreditation of persons authorised to conduct inspections and issue the energy certification of buildings; and provides economic incentives for improved energy efficiency.

There are a number of different funds administered by the Piedmont Region to support energy efficient buildings, including grants for demonstration projects which incorporate innovate technical or management features, for constructing or developing district heating, and to improve energy efficiency in public buildings. Each commune implements its own building regulations, with their own sustainable building code based on regional guidelines. Certain elements are integrated from national laws and decrees, but in principle there is no national system of building standards. The municipality, where the flagship project is located, is therefore responsible for building regulations.

4 Identification and characterisation of EeB relevant policies

A so-called snowball process was used to identify public policies relevant to energy efficient building projects in each of the four countries home to a flagship project, namely Italy, Poland, Spain and the United Kingdom. Initial information on relevant policies was gathered through a preliminary literature search and responses from interview respondents. The policy documents and associated commentary captured in this exercise in turn acted as referrals to assist in the discovery of further policies and so on until further policies were not forthcoming. This iterative process was complemented by periodic cross checking of policies between the target countries *i.e.*, where a policy was identified in one country, a focused search was made for corresponding policies in the other countries. Finally the list of policies identified for each country was reviewed in a round-robin fashion by team members including UMBRELLA partners with knowledge of the specific countries.

Following on the work of Koeppel *et al.* (2007) and Koeppel & Üрге-Vorsatz (2007), the policies were grouped into five broad groups as illustrated in Table 2 below.

Control and regulation		Market-based	Fiscal	Support
Normative	Mandatory informative			
Appliance standards Building codes Procurement regulations Energy efficiency obligations and quotas	Mandatory audits Utility demand-side management programmes Mandatory labelling and certificates	Energy performance contracting Cooperative procurements Energy efficiency certificate schemes Clean Development Mechanism (Kyoto Protocol) Joint implementation (Kyoto Protocol)	Carbon taxes Tax exemptions Public benefit charges Subsidies, grants and subsidised loans	Voluntary labelling and certificates Voluntary and negotiated agreements Public leadership programmes Information and education initiatives Detailed billing and disclosure programmes

Table 2: Examples of policy instrument classification (after Koeppel & Üрге-Vorsatz 2007)

The policies were labelled for identification purposes, following the codes in Table 3 and Table 4 and numbered sequentially. For example I-N-01 refers to the first normative policy instrument listed for Italy. The complete compiled list of public policies relevant to energy efficient building for the four countries is included as Appendix I.

Country	Code
Italy	I
Poland	P
Spain	S
United Kingdom	UK

Table 3: Country identification codes for polices

Policy category	Code
Normative policy instruments	N
Mandatory informative policy instruments	MI
Market based policy instruments	MB
Fiscal policy instruments	F
Support policy instruments	S

Table 4: Identification codes for polices categories

The identified policies were then characterised on the basis of a number of performance metrics (Energy Efficiency Potential; Emissions Reduction Effectiveness; Cost Effectiveness; Impact on Innovation; and Potential for synergy), based on the assessments of Koepfel & Ürge-Vorsatz (2007), Vreuls (2005), and informed by Noailly (2012), Vine *et al.* (2003) and Tanaka (2011). The following sections present the performance characterisation of the identified policies for these different metrics.

4.1 Effectiveness – energy efficiency & emissions reduction

Koepfel *et al.* (2007) assessed the effectiveness of different types of policies in increasing energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions within the built environment. Initially, they attempted to assess the policies' effectiveness quantitatively, either in absolute or in relative terms (*i.e.*, compared to a logical baseline, such as total national emissions). However, this proved unfeasible due to lack of baselines and differences in the temporal and spatial scale of the case studies and of the policy instruments. Therefore, in their contribution to the IPCC 2007 report (Levine *et al.* 2007: 421-435) and, later, in a chapter for a report for the United Nations Environmental Programme (Koepfel *et al.* 2007; Koepfel & Ürge-Vorsatz 2007), they took a more qualitative view, assigning relative non-numeric grades (high, medium, Low) to policy instruments for their effectiveness in reducing energy use and GHG emissions.

Koepfel *et al.* (2007) recommend implementing measures for achieving three different levels of building performance: (1) *a minimum performance level*, mandatory for all buildings which can be reached through minimum standards; (2) *a best practice level* which is often used as a basis for defining subsidies, tax exemptions, loans *etc.*; and, finally, (3) *a state-of-the art level* which is often set a long-term target to provide incentives to industry to further improve (see also Klinckenberg & Sunikka 2006).

Koepfel *et al.* (2007) concluded that appliance standards, building codes, voluntary labelling and tax exemptions achieved the highest GHG emission reductions. They found that support, information and voluntary action policy instruments vary significantly in their effectiveness. Generally speaking, their effectiveness is not great; however, awareness-raising instruments can have a role to play. They are important to complement other instruments by limiting rebound effects. Voluntary instruments are less effective than mandatory ones. Public leadership programs are often effective and important, not only for the public sector. Green procurement policies are also effective.

Using the Koepfel *et al.* determinations, the identified policies (see Appendix I for details) in Italy, Poland, Spain and the United Kingdom were categorised in terms of effectiveness in increasing energy efficiency and of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The results of which are presented below as Table 5 and Table 6 respectively.

Table 5: Energy efficiency effectiveness of Identified policies

Category	Policy Instrument	Energy Efficiency Effectiveness ¹²	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
Normative	Building Codes	High	I-N-01	P-N-04	S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04 S-N-05	UK-N-01 UK-N-03 UK-N-04
	Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas	High	I-N-02 I-N-03 I-N-04 I-N-05	P-N-02 P-N-03	S-N-03	
	Appliance Standards	High		P-N-01		UK-N-02 UK-N-05
Mandatory Informative	Mandatory Audit Requirement	High, Variable	I-MI-02			UK-MI-01
	Labelling and Certification Programmes	Medium	I-MI-01 I-MI-03 I-MI-04	P-MI-03	S-MI-01 S-MI-02 S-MI-03	UK-MI-02 UK-MI-03
	(Utility) Demand Side Management Programmes	High	I-MI-05 I-MI-06 I-MI-07 I-MI-08 I-MI-09 I-MI-10			UK-MI-04
Market Based	Energy performance contracting support	High			S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03 S-MB-04	UK-MB-02
	Cooperative Procurement	High	I-MB-04			UK-MB-01
	Energy Efficiency / White Certificates	Low	I-MB-06 I-MB-07 I-MB-08	P-MB-01		

¹² The effectiveness evaluation derived from Koepfel & Ürge-Vorsatz (2007)

Category	Policy Instrument	Energy Efficiency Effectiveness ¹²	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
	Kyoto Protocol Flexible Mech.	Low	I-MB-01 I-MB-02			
Fiscal	Taxation (on CO ₂ , fuels)	Low, medium		P-F-17	S-F-11	UK-F-04 UK-F-05
	Tax exemptions / reductions	Medium	I-F-01 I-F-02 I-F-03 I-F-04			
	Public benefit charges	Medium		P-F-01 P-F-07 P-F-08 P-F-09 P-F-12 P-F-13	S-F-08 S-F-09	
	Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans	High	I-F-05 I-F-06	P-F-02 P-F-03 P-F-04 P-F-05 P-F-06 P-F-10 P-F-11 P-F-14 P-F-15 P-F-16 P-F-18	S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03 S-F-04 S-F-05 S-F-06 S-F-07 S-F-10 S-F-12 S-F-13	UK-F-01 UK-F-02 UK-F-03 UK-F-06 UK-F-07 UK-F-08 UK-F-09 UK-F-10
Support	Voluntary and negotiated agreements	Medium, High	I-S-07	P-S-01	S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15	UK-S-10 UK-S-11 UK-S-12 UK-S-17 UK-S-23
	Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations	Medium, High	I-S-01 I-S-03 I-S-05 I-S-06	P-S-02 P-S-04	S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05 S-S-06	UK-S-01 UK-S-15 UK-S-18 UK-S-19

Category	Policy Instrument	Energy Efficiency Effectiveness ¹²	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
					S-S-11 S-S-13 S-S-14 S-S-16 S-S-17	
	Education and information programmes	Medium	I-S-02 I-S-04	P-S-03 P-S-05	S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12	UK-S-02 UK-S-06 UK-S-07 UK-S-08 UK-S-09 UK-S-20 UK-S-21 UK-S-22
	Detailed billing and disclosure programmes	Medium, High				UK-S-03 UK-S-04 UK-S-05 UK-S-15

Table 6: Emission reduction effectiveness of identified policies

Category	Policy Instrument	Emission Reduction Effectiveness ¹³	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
Normative	Building Codes	High	I-N-01	P-N-04	S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04 S-N-05	UK-N-01 UK-N-03 UK-N-04
	Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas	High	I-N-02 I-N-03 I-N-04 I-N-05	P-N-02 P-N-03	S-N-03	
	Appliance Standards	High		P-N-01		UK-N-02 UK-N-05

¹³ After Koepfel & Ürgel-Vorsatz (2007)

Category	Policy Instrument	Emission Reduction Effectiveness ¹³	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
Mandatory Informative	Mandatory Audit Requirement	High (but variable)	I-MI-02			UK-MI-01
	Labelling and Certification Programmes	Medium / High	I-MI-01 I-MI-03 I-MI-04	P-MI-03	S-MI-01 S-MI-02 S-MI-03	UK-MI-02 UK-MI-03
	(utility) Demand Side Management Programmes	High	I-MI-05 I-MI-06 I-MI-07 I-MI-08 I-MI-09 I-MI-10			UK-MI-04
Market Based	Energy performance contracting support	High			S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03 S-MB-04	UK-MB-02
	Cooperative Procurement	High	I-MB-04			UK-MB-01
	Energy Efficiency Certificate Schemes / White Certificates	Medium	I-MB-06 I-MB-07 I-MB-08	P-MB-01		
	Kyoto Protocol Flexible Mechanisms	Low	I-MB-01 I-MB-02			
Fiscal	Taxation (on CO ₂ , fuels)	Low		P-F-17	S-F-11	UK-F-04 UK-F-05
	Tax exemptions / reductions	High	I-F-01 I-F-02 I-F-03 I-F-04			
	Public benefit charges	Medium		P-F-01 P-F-07 P-F-08 P-F-09	S-F-08 S-F-09	

Category	Policy Instrument	Emission Reduction Effectiveness ¹³	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
				P-F-12 P-F-13		
	Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans	High	I-F-05 I-F-06	P-F-02 P-F-03 P-F-04 P-F-05 P-F-06 P-F-10 P-F-11 P-F-14 P-F-15 P-F-16 P-F-18	S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03 S-F-04 S-F-05 S-F-06 S-F-07 S-F-10 S-F-12 S-F-13	UK-F-01 UK-F-02 UK-F-03 UK-F-06 UK-F-07 UK-F-08 UK-F-09 UK-F-10
Support	Voluntary and negotiated agreements	Medium/ High	I-S-07	P-S-01	S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15	UK-S-10 UK-S-11 UK-S-12 UK-S-17 UK-S-23
	Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations	Medium/ High	I-S-01 I-S-03 I-S-05 I-S-06	P-S-02 P-S-04	S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05 S-S-06 S-S-11 S-S-13 S-S-14 S-S-16 S-S-17	UK-S-01 UK-S-15 UK-S-18 UK-S-19
	Education and information programmes	Low/ Medium	I-S-02 I-S-04	P-S-03 P-S-05	S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12	UK-S-02 UK-S-06 UK-S-07 UK-S-08 UK-S-09 UK-S-20 UK-S-21

Category	Policy Instrument	Emission Reduction Effectiveness ¹³	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
						UK-S-22
	Detailed billing and disclosure programmes	Medium				UK-S-03 UK-S-04 UK-S-05 UK-S-15

4.2 Cost effectiveness

In addition to considering energy efficiency and emissions impact, Koepfel *et al.* (2007) also graded the cost-effectiveness of policy instruments. They considered cost-effectiveness from a societal perspective, taking into account when possible the direct costs and benefits from the policy-making perspective, but excluding indirect or external costs (not for lack of relevance, but because they were deemed impossible to quantify). Many policy evaluations assess the cost-effectiveness of energy savings according to the cost required to conserve energy (capital costs and investment costs) only. In comparing the four broad categories of instruments, regulatory and control instruments were found to be the most cost effective policy instruments with particularly high negative costs (*i.e.*, very low costs of mitigation, although it is likely that the rebound effect limits overall effectiveness, so that correct enforcement is necessary) (see also Tanaka 2011). Within this category, appliance standards, energy efficiency obligations and building codes were especially effective. Appliance standards and energy efficiency obligations were also very cost-effective.

Koepfel *et al.* (2007) identified appliance standards, utility DSM programs, public benefit charges, energy efficiency obligations and mandatory labelling as the most cost-effective policy tools, achieving significant GHG emission reductions at negative costs. Appliance standards were very cost-effective with negative costs of US\$65-190 /tCO₂. Economic instruments are still difficult to evaluate since some of them, such as the Kyoto Flexible Mechanisms¹⁴ and the White Certificate are still relatively new. Their effectiveness and cost-effectiveness depends significantly on the policy instrument that is being selected. Both the

¹⁴ Emissions Trading; Clean Development Mechanism (see <http://cdm.unfccc.int>); Joint implementation (see <http://ji.unfccc.int/index.html>)

effectiveness and the cost-effectiveness of project-based mechanisms, such as the Kyoto flexible mechanisms are currently limited. This is probably due to high transaction costs involved with small projects in the building sector. Fiscal instruments and incentives also lead to very diverging results: subsidies are not cost-effective in contrast to the reviewed cases in tax exemptions (income taxation). However, they are useful to kick-start the market for new energy efficient products.

Table 7: Cost Effectiveness of Identified policies

Category	Policy Instrument	Cost Effectiveness ¹⁵	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
Normative	Building Codes	Medium	I-N-01	P-N-04	S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04 S-N-05	UK-N-01 UK-N-03 UK-N-04
	Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas	High	I-N-02 I-N-03 I-N-04 I-N-05	P-N-02 P-N-03	S-N-03	
	Appliance Standards	High		P-N-01		UK-N-02 UK-N-05
Mandatory Informative	Mandatory Audit Requirement	Medium	I-MI-02			UK-MI-01
	Labelling and Certification Programmes	High	I-MI-01 I-MI-03 I-MI-04	P-MI-03	S-MI-01 S-MI-02 S-MI-03	UK-MI-02 UK-MI-03
	(utility) Demand Side Management Programmes	High	I-MI-05 I-MI-06 I-MI-07 I-MI-08 I-MI-09 I-MI-10			UK-MI-04
Market Based	Energy performance contracting support	Medium			S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03 S-MB-04	UK-MB-02

¹⁵ After Koeppel & Ürge-Vorsatz (2007)

Category	Policy Instrument	Cost Effectiveness ²⁵	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
	Cooperative Procurement	Medium/ High	I-MB-04			UK-MB-01
	Energy Efficiency Certificate Schemes / White Certificates	High/ Medium	I-MB-06 I-MB-07 I-MB-08	P-MB-01		
	Kyoto Protocol Flexible Mechanisms	Low	I-MB-01 I-MB-02			
Fiscal	Taxation (on CO ₂ , fuels)	Low		P-F-17	S-F-11	UK-F-04 UK-F-05
	Tax exemptions / reductions	High	I-F-01 I-F-02 I-F-03 I-F-04			
	Public benefit charges	High		P-F-01 P-F-07 P-F-08 P-F-09 P-F-12 P-F-13	S-F-08 S-F-09	
	Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans	Low	I-F-05 I-F-06	P-F-02 P-F-03 P-F-04 P-F-05 P-F-06 P-F-10 P-F-11 P-F-14 P-F-15 P-F-16 P-F-18	S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03 S-F-04 S-F-05 S-F-06 S-F-07 S-F-10 S-F-12 S-F-13	UK-F-01 UK-F-02 UK-F-03 UK-F-06 UK-F-07 UK-F-08 UK-F-09 UK-F-10

Category	Policy Instrument	Cost Effectiveness ²⁵	Italy	Poland	Spain	UK
Support Policies	Voluntary and negotiated agreements	Medium	I-S-07	P-S-01	S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15	UK-S-10 UK-S-11 UK-S-12 UK-S-17 UK-S-23
	Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations	High/ Medium	I-S-01 I-S-03 I-S-05 I-S-06	P-S-02 P-S-04	S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05 S-S-06 S-S-11 S-S-13 S-S-14 S-S-16 S-S-17	UK-S-01 UK-S-15 UK-S-18 UK-S-19
	Education and information programmes	Medium/ High	I-S-02 I-S-04	P-S-03 P-S-05	S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12	UK-S-02 UK-S-06 UK-S-07 UK-S-08 UK-S-09 UK-S-20 UK-S-21 UK-S-22
	Detailed billing and disclosure programmes	Medium				UK-S-03 UK-S-04 UK-S-05 UK-S-15

4.3 Potential Innovation Support

Different policy approaches can either enhance or stifle innovation in energy efficient building activities. Crawford and French (2008), for example speak of the potential of the planning system to inhibit innovation on hand, while on the other hand also having the potential to ‘stimulate new lines of research and development, and new corporate and community endeavours in shaping the built environment’. Williamson and Lynch-Wood

(2012) argue the need for different types of policy instruments to bring about environmental improvements by both actors which occupy ‘beyond compliance’ positions and those who may be performance laggards. Including voluntary measure to stimulate strong innovation (*i.e.*, radical changes) in those who are beyond compliance, and more regulatory approaches to force incremental changes building on existing solutions (*i.e.*, weak innovation) in less proactive actors. Table 8 below presents an assessment of potential for the different policy instrument types to support innovation.

Table 8: Innovation potential of Identified policies

Category	Policy Instrument	Potential for weak innovation	Potential for strong innovation	Policy examples from study countries	
Normative	Building Codes	Medium	Low	I-N-01 P-N-04 S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04	S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04 S-N-05
	Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas	Medium	Medium	I-N-02 I-N-03 I-N-04 I-N-05	S-N-03
	Appliance Standards	Medium	Low	P-N-01 UK-N-02	
Mandatory Informative	Mandatory Audit Requirement	Low	Medium	I-MI-02	
	Labelling and Certification Programmes	Medium	High	I-MI-01 I-MI-03 I-MI-04 P-MI-03 S-MI-01	S-MI-01 S-MI-02 S-MI-03
	(utility) Demand Side Management Programmes	Medium	Medium	I-MI-05 I-MI-06 I-MI-07 I-MI-08	
Market Based	Energy performance contracting support	Medium	High	S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03	S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03

Category	Policy Instrument	Potential for weak innovation	Potential for strong innovation	Policy examples from study countries	
					S-MB-04
	Cooperative Procurement	Low	High	I-MB-04	
	Energy Efficiency Certificate Schemes / White Certificates	Low	Medium	I-MB-06 I-MB-07	
	Kyoto Protocol Flexible Mechanisms	Low	Medium	I-MB-01	
				P-F-17 S-F-11	
Fiscal	Taxation (on CO ₂ , fuels)	Medium	High	I-F-01 I-F-02	S-F-11
	Tax exemptions / reductions	Medium	High	P-F-01 P-F-07 P-F-08 P-F-09	
	Public benefit charges	Low	Medium	I-F-05 I-F-06 P-F-02 P-F-03 P-F-04 P-F-05 P-F-06 P-F-10 P-F-11 P-F-14 P-F-15 P-F-16 P-F-18 S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03	S-F-08 S-F-09
	Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans	Low	Medium	I-S-07 P-S-01 S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15	S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03 S-F-04 S-F-05

Category	Policy Instrument	Potential for weak innovation	Potential for strong innovation	Policy examples from study countries	
					S-F-06 S-F-07 S-F-10 S-F-12 S-F-13
Support Policies	Voluntary and negotiated agreements	Low	Medium	I-S-01 I-S-03 I-S-05 I-S-06 P-S-02 P-S-04 S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05	S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15
	Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations	Low	High	I-S-02 I-S-04 P-S-03 P-S-05 S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12 UK-S-02	S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05 S-S-06 S-S-11 S-S-13 S-S-14 S-S-16 S-S-17
	Education and information programmes	Medium	Medium (high)	UK-S-03 UK-S-04	S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12
	Detailed billing and disclosure	Low	Medium (high)		

4.4 Potential for Synergy with other policies

There have been attempts to devise optimal policy mixes in many contexts before (see, for example within the EU, Görlach 2014; Klein *et al.* 2005). Clearly, no single instrument can capture the entire economic and low-cost mitigation potential alone, and there is a need to

produce a mix of policies that optimises outcomes. Policy mixes create policy synergies, thereby increasing the effectiveness of separate policies and decreasing unwanted outcomes: the mix is more than the sum of its parts. The question is then how such mixes can be identified. A portfolio of instruments is necessary to take advantage of synergistic effects. For this to happen, policy mixes need take account of the diverse barriers, specific local conditions, cultural traditions and other factors that may co-determine or impact the effectiveness of policies. While the need for a mix of policy measures is easily and intuitively understood, the question is how such mixes can be made optimally efficient (Tanaka 2011; Bernstein et al. 2007). Table 9 below provides examples of the policy mix potential associated with the policy instruments identified in the four study countries.

Table 9: Examples of synergy potential of identified policies

Category	Policy Instrument	Policy examples from study countries		Example of potential policy mix ¹⁶
Normative	Building Codes	I-N-01 P-N-04 S-N-01 S-N-02 S-N-04	S-N-05 UK-N-01 UK-N-03 UK-N-04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labelling & Certification Programmes • Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans • Education and information programmes
	Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas	I-N-02 I-N-03 I-N-04 I-N-05	P-N-02 P-N-03 S-N-03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and information programmes
	Appliance Standards	P-N-01 UK-N-02	UK-N-05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and information programmes • Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans
Mandatory Informative	Mandatory Audit Requirement	I-MI-02	UK-MI-01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education & information programmes • Tax exemptions / reductions • Voluntary and negotiated agreements
	Labelling and Certification Programmes	I-MI-01 I-MI-03 I-MI-04 P-MI-03 S-MI-01	S-MI-02 S-MI-03 UK-MI-02 UK-MI-03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building codes • Education and information programmes
	Demand Side Management	I-MI-05 I-MI-06	I-MI-09 I-MI-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and information programmes • Mandatory Audit Requirement

¹⁶ After Vreuls (2005), Tanaka (2011) and Koeppel, Ürge-Vorsatz & Czako (2007)

Category	Policy Instrument	Policy examples from study countries		Example of potential policy mix ¹⁶
	Programmes (utility)	I-MI-07 I-MI-08	UK-MI-04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans
Market Based	Energy performance contracting support	S-MB-01 S-MB-02 S-MB-03	S-MB-04 UK-MB-02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations
	Coop. Procurement	I-MB-04	UK-MB-01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labelling & Certification Programmes
	Energy Efficiency Certificate Schemes / White Certificates	I-MB-06 I-MB-07	I-MB-08 P-MB-01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Labelling & Certification Programmes Mandatory Audit Requirement
	KP Flexible Mechan.	I-MB-01	I-MB-02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory Audit Requirement
Fiscal	Taxation (on CO ₂ , fuels)	P-F-17 S-F-11	UK-F-04 UK-F-05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory Audit Requirement Tax exemptions / reductions
	Tax exemptions / reductions	I-F-01 I-F-02	I-F-03 I-F-04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taxation (on CO₂, fuels) Labelling & Certification Programmes Mandatory Audit Requirement Voluntary and negotiated agreements
	Public benefit charges	P-F-01 P-F-07 P-F-08 P-F-09	P-F-12 P-F-13 S-F-08 S-F-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory Audit Requirement Education and information programmes
	Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans	I-F-05 I-F-06 P-F-02 P-F-03 P-F-04 P-F-05 P-F-06 P-F-10 P-F-11 P-F-14 P-F-15 P-F-16 P-F-18 S-F-01 S-F-02 S-F-03	S-F-04 S-F-05 S-F-06 S-F-07 S-F-10 S-F-12 S-F-13 UK-F-01 UK-F-02 UK-F-03 UK-F-06 UK-F-07 UK-F-08 UK-F-09 UK-F-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building codes Labelling & Certification Programmes Education and information programmes

Category	Policy Instrument	Policy examples from study countries		Example of potential policy mix ¹⁶
Support Policies	Voluntary and negotiated agreements	I-S-07 P-S-01 S-S-09 S-S-10 S-S-15	UK-S-10 UK-S-11 UK-S-12 UK-S-17 UK-S-23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax exemptions / reductions • Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans • Mandatory Audit Requirement
	Public leadership programmes including procurement regulations	I-S-01 I-S-03 I-S-05 I-S-06 P-S-02 P-S-04 S-S-01 S-S-02 S-S-03 S-S-04 S-S-05	S-S-06 S-S-11 S-S-13 S-S-14 S-S-16 S-S-17 UK-S-01 UK-S-15 UK-S-18 UK-S-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy performance contracting support • Building Codes • Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas • Appliance Standards • Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans
	Education and information programmes	I-S-02 I-S-04 P-S-03 P-S-05 S-S-07 S-S-08 S-S-12 UK-S-02	UK-S-06 UK-S-07 UK-S-08 UK-S-09 UK-S-20 UK-S-21 UK-S-22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Codes • Energy Efficiency Obligations and Quotas • Appliance Standards • Energy performance contracting support • Capital subsidies, grants, subsidised loans
	Detailed billing and disclosure programmes	UK-S-03 UK-S-04	UK-S-05 UK-S-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education and information programmes • Taxation (on CO₂, fuels...) • Labelling & Certification Programmes

5 National innovation governance systems

As discussed in section 2.2.4 Innovation systems are “socio-technical configurations of actors, rules, physical infrastructure and their relations.” (Negro *et al.* 2012). The following sections present an overview of the governance of innovation within the four study countries: Italy, Poland, Spain and the United Kingdom.

5.1 Kingdom of Spain

The Spanish government has prioritised R&D in recent years and funding has been protected or increased annually despite economic difficulties. This prioritisation has been accompanied by major reforms, undertaken in the Law on Science, Technology and Innovation (2011), to give Spain a more robust system of innovation governance. The main responsibility for innovation governance in Spain resides with the Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN), created in April 2008, which spent 68% of the state budget on R&D in 2011. The Ministry of Education also has some responsibilities for research policies in respect of the university sector. The Ministry of Industry, Tourism and Commerce (MICYT), which spent 26.8% of the state innovation budget in 2011, liaises with industry and is especially involved in policies to foster the Information and Communication Technology (ICT sector).

The Ministry of Science and Innovation has chief responsibility for the design of R&D and innovation policy, including the multi-annual Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and the State Innovation Strategy 2010-2015. It develops the plans subject to the approval of the Inter-ministerial Commission on Science and Technology (CICYT). The commission is chaired by the prime minister and includes high-level representatives of the ministries involved in R&D. The CICYT has two consultative bodies: the Scientific and Technology Policy Council (STPC) and the Advisory Council of Science and Innovation (ACSI). The STPC coordinates R&D and innovation policies between national and regional administrations; half its members are representatives of the regional governments. The ACST is designed to ensure the participation of the research community and social and economic interests (including businesses and trade unions) in innovation governance. Both are involved in the design of the strategic plans which set out the framework for Spanish R&D and innovation policy, under the overall coordination of the Ministry of Science and Innovation.

The legal framework for innovation is established by the Law on Science, Technology and Innovation (2011), which reformed innovation and R&D governance in Spain and has a

particular aim of integrating technology and innovation with scientific research. The chief policy instruments for innovation in Spain are the State Innovation Strategy (2010-15); Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology (2013-20); and the Plan AVANZA2 (2011-15). The first two in particular have a strong focus on sustainable development. The 2011 Law also established a State Research Agency charged with funding R&D. The Centre for Industrial Technological Development (CDTI –dependent on the MICINN) remains the agency tasked with implementing most innovation-oriented policy measures and funds innovation that is nearer to the market. There is no government unit specialising in providing strategic R&D policy intelligence. Instead, a variety of individuals, regional representatives, scientific umbrella organisations and sectoral business associations participate in the policy-making process on an *ad hoc* basis. Moreover, systematic evaluation of R&D and innovation policy has yet to be developed in the Spanish context.

5.2 United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

Successive UK governments in recent years have worked to develop Britain's innovation policy, with a focus on funding science and knowledge transfer and increasing commercialisation. The governance structure for innovation has also been reformed with the aim of maintaining scientific excellence while improving links with industry. At the core of innovation governance in the UK is the Government Office for Science, headed by the Government Chief Scientific Advisor, the office is based in the Department of Business Innovation and Skills (BIS) and advises the government on policy and decision-making. Operating under the Department of BIS are the Higher Education Funding Council for England, which funds universities and higher education institutes; the research councils, seven of which are responsible for investing public money in research in different areas including science, technology and engineering; and the Technology Strategy Board (recently rebranded as Innovate UK), who seek to accelerate economic growth by stimulating and supporting business-led innovation. The latter has recently expanded its role and is currently the only public sector agency responsible for innovation with a cross-economy, cross-sectoral remit, covering the whole United Kingdom.

The Government Chief Scientific Advisor is independent of all ministries (though they are administratively housed in the Office of Science and Technology) and has no budget of their own. They have the right of access to the Prime Minister, and can therefore review – and, with the Prime Minister's support, overrule – any aspect of science-related policy. The UK

government also receives advice from the Council for Science and Technology, an external group of high-level stakeholders. This body advises the Prime Minister on science and technology policy issues which cut across the responsibilities of government departments. The council is supported by a secretariat based in the Government Office for Science and is co-chaired by the Chief Scientific Advisor.

After the Conservative/Liberal Democratic coalition government came to power in 2010 a number of changes to innovation governance took place, including the scrapping of the Regional Development Agencies (hitherto responsible for driving innovation policy at the regional level). These were replaced with Local Economic Partnerships, which are consortia of local authorities responsible for economic development. The Technology Strategy Board was given increased responsibilities including that of regional innovation support. The coalition also oversaw the establishment of Technology and Innovation Centres, which are intended to help commercialise new technologies and bridge the gap between universities and business.

The Science and Innovation Investment Framework (SIIF) provides a long-term policy context for the prioritisation of expenditure on science and technology. The other major policy framework is the Innovation and Research Strategy for Growth (2011), whose priorities include accelerating the commercialisation of emerging technologies and improving the interface between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and business.

5.3 Republic of Poland

In 2010, Polish investment in research and development was 0.20% of GDP, among the lowest in the OECD; however the government aims for this to reach 1.7% of GDP by 2020. Links between industry and science have traditionally been weak – a legacy of the planned economy which existed under communism. The principal responsibility for the design of innovation policy lies with the Economy Department of the Ministry of Economy and the Strategy Department of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. The Ministry of Science and Higher Education is responsible for science and technology design and the Ministry of Economy is in charge of innovation policy. Implementation is the responsibility of two key agencies: the National Research and Development Centre (NCBiR), which is responsible for the management and implementation of strategic scientific research and development programmes, and the National Science Centre (NSC), which is responsible for

overseeing basic research projects. The NCBiR was reformed in 2010 and gained new powers as part of an effort to improve public-private co-operation and increase private R&D spending. The Polish Agency for Entrepreneurship Development (PARP), supervised by the Ministry of Economy, is co-responsible for implementing innovation policy.

In addition, two committees have been recently established at the MSHE, namely the Committee for Science Policy and the Committee for Evaluation of Scientific Institutions. Among the main responsibilities of the former is to support the Minister in preparation of documents concerning the development of science, technology and innovation policy and the drafting of the state budget for the support of science. The Committee for Evaluation of Scientific Institutions is tasked with the evaluation of scientific institutions. Most funding for research and development is channelled through the Polish Agency for Enterprise Development (PARP), and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education.

The Strategy for the Innovativeness & Effectiveness of the Economy (2012-20) represents a major development in innovation policy. Previously attempts had been made but had never resulted in a unified strategy. Other important policy documents include Poland 2030: Third Wave of Modernity; National Reform Programme (NRP); and Innovative Economy 2007-13. The new Science Development Programme and Entrepreneurship Development Programme aims to promote a knowledge-based economy building on current strengths, emerging technologies and smart specialisation. The National Foresight Programme, Poland 2030, and InSight2030 outline potential scenarios for the next two decades.

5.4 Italian Republic

As recently as 2010, Italian investment in research and development was just 1.26% of GDP, about half of the OECD average. Research in Italy is characterised by weak industry-science linkages, and R&D and innovation capacity is concentrated in northern and central regions of the country. In recent years public funding of research and innovation has increased, albeit from a low base, especially in the period following the economic crisis.

The Ministry for Economic Development (MISE) is in charge of industrial innovation, and the Ministry for Education, Universities and Research (MIUR) is responsible for higher education and for promoting research at national and international level. The MIUR is organised into twelve directorates, including a General Directorate for Internationalisation of Research and a General Directorate for the Coordination and Development of Research. The MIUR also has

oversight of a number of national scientific organisations, including the National Research Council (CNR). The National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes (ANVUR) has operated under MIUR since 2010. MIUR coordinates the preparation of the National Plan for Research, the main governmental tool for R&D and innovation planning.

The 2010-2012 National Plan for Research created a new structure, Coordination Activities of Italian Research (ACR), acting under the aegis of MIUR, which is tasked with improving the coordination of national research activity. The Agency for the Diffusion of Technologies for Innovation, created by the 2006 Financial Law, is also charged with improving the coordination of innovation policies, both between ministries and between ministries and regions. Evaluation of innovation policy takes place mostly within the framework of the National Research Plan. Data on the various projects, which have been funded is collected and evaluated in terms of implementation, physical realisation and the effectiveness of the programmes.

The principal framework for innovation policy in Italy is the National Plan for Research, the current version of which runs from 2014-20 and is supported with funding of €900 million per annum. The plan is built around eleven important ‘societal challenges’, which include ‘secure, clean and efficient energy’, ‘smart, green and integrated transport’, and ‘climate action, resource efficiency and raw materials’. Approved by the Inter-Ministry Committee for Economic Planning (CIPE), the plan is administered by Programme Committees, which include representatives of public and private bodies. Italy’s regions have responsibility for defining specific guidelines and programmes for their own areas within the overall framework of the plan.

Various initiatives in recent years have aimed to bridge the gap between academia and industry. The National Research Plan (which is renewed every third year) aimed to promote research by strengthening business co-operation with the public sector and supporting the internationalisation of research. The Industry 2015 programme (2006-15) aims to support business networks and industrial innovation projects, including through government funding. In pursuit of these goals, technological districts and high technology poles as well as public-private laboratories have been established in different parts of the country. Despite efforts to improve innovation governance, considerable fragmentation persists and there is a need to improve the co-ordination of R&D and innovation policy both across government ministries and between central government and the regions.

6 Barriers to innovation

6.1 Stakeholder's Viewpoints

Within work package 3 of UMBRELLA, a series of over 100 in-depth interviews were conducted with relevant energy efficient building stakeholders, across the hubs of activity, in ten EU countries – the four countries home to flagship projects (Italy, Poland, Spain, and the United Kingdom) and six additional countries selected to widen the scope of the engagement (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland, and Sweden). The interviews were carried out face-to-face, using a semi-structured interview schedule and the dialogue recorded and transcribed. The transcripts were subsequently qualitatively analysed by means of a grounded approach using iterative ‘coding’, with the aid of NVivo qualitative data analysis software. NVivo provided a platform to collect and organise the content from the interviews and assisted in its analysis, through use of the software’s search, query and visualization tools¹⁷. The following list comprises the findings from this interview process wherein the respondents forwarded their opinion on the issues associated with, and barriers to, innovation for energy efficient building activity. There was general consensus among respondents that the construction industry suffered from a lack of innovation from all stakeholders: building owners, contractors, financiers, and designers, and that this lack of innovation stifled measures that often requires ‘outside of the box’ thinking.

Waste

- Energy efficient construction new building and retrofit projects increasingly involve the use of novel materials. Such materials are typically high performing and long lasting; however they are regularly non-recyclable and so the problem of dealing with the waste is left to the future. As the end-of-life phase of the materials can therefore not be modelled, whole-life energy calculations are not meaningful in any way – this is especially so in the case of plastics, chemicals and what Braungart and McDonough (2010) call ‘monstrous hybrids’.

Education and Training

- The low turnover of building stock means that the majority of future construction work will comprise the renovation of, including energy retrofit to, existing buildings. However the focus of education and training for the construction professions and

¹⁷ For further information on the interview process and subsequent analysis and interpretation, please refer to UMBRELLA deliverables: D3.2 *Report on Stakeholder Interviews* and D3.3 *Report on Data Analysis*

crafts remains the ‘ideal’ project involving a new build on a green field site. The preparation of the key members of the future construction workforce would appear therefore to be at variance with the needs of the industry.

- There is a shortage of the skilled personnel required to mitigate the performance risks associated with energy efficient building projects.
- The role of designers is changing, and there appears to be a gap in the market for some sort of interdisciplinary role as an Architectural Engineering Physicist, to bridge the gap between the professions that currently exists. For cost saving purposes it is often the task of one or two professionals to fulfil all the roles of architect, engineer, and building physicist in order to achieve the best energy performance – however, very few people possess all three skill sets.
- Lack of knowledge on the part of the building owners may mean that they do not have sufficient understanding to seek out the right information, and the most appropriate personnel for the job.
- Lack of education and information on energy saving were cited by many as barriers in the case of all stakeholders, from owners, to designers, to builders.
- What works for one project will not necessarily work for the next; there is always a learning curve, even for the most experienced professionals and builders.

Finance / Business Case

- The boom and bust cycles of the construction industry, especially most recent bust cycle, was cited as a major barrier to innovation. Construction and design firms have gone out of business, potential clients and developers cannot secure finance to build or renovate, and where they can, budgets tend to be very tight, with cost overriding other concerns.
- The return on investment (ROI), or financial payback period usually has to be very short for an energy efficient project to get the approval to go ahead, especially where there is no additional funding such as a grant, or where there is a cultural disinclination to take on debt.
- Interest rates for green loans were considered too high in some countries, and grant application processes are considered to be onerous and demanding.
- Speculative real estate investors, ones with very large building portfolios, have no

real interest in the actual buildings, and it is very difficult to engage with them and get them to consider the energy use of their buildings.

- The perception of risk is very high at the moment, which leads to very conservative building and spending practices, and is a big problem for existing buildings as there is always an element of risk and uncertainty when dealing with an old building for any type of construction work, but especially for energy retro-fitting as many problems will only be visible once the project gets on site.
- In the current economic climate in the construction industry many projects are publicly funded, and the design and construction teams must compete in architectural competitions and tender processes to get the job. This is usually done at significant cost to the design team, but when there are less private projects to absorb the costs of entering competitions and tenders, this generally excludes smaller or newer businesses, and may also be excluding more energy efficient proposals in order to get the lowest possible tender price.
- Many stakeholders are unaware of lifecycle analysis, and are unwilling to pay for it.
- Split incentives / Competing objectives of stakeholders.
- The human dimension: cultural barriers to behavioural change; habitual behaviours; rebound factor
- Lack of interest in small energy retrofits was also cited where builders do not want to waste time in class learning about energy when they could be on site earning money, and where large firms would rather be working on big state funded infrastructural projects with more financial stability.
- Retrofitting may not be practical in existing buildings where occupants may need to be re-housed, or where businesses, schools, or hospitals would need to be temporarily closed down to facilitate works.

Stakeholder Relationship & Communications

- Communication across the project team is not always very clear, different stakeholders all want and need different things from a project, and they do not always communicate their goals and values clearly and appropriately.
- Despite the fact that buildings have long lifespans, there is generally almost no relationship at all between the contractor and the client once the building is

occupied. The clients/occupants are usually left to their own devices to manage and maintain the building for the rest of its lifespan, and poor management and maintenance can lead to many energy inefficiencies.

- As development of a brand new profession is a long process, in the mean time much improved co-ordination and collaboration between the various design roles is needed, but is unfortunately often lacking. Several of the interviewees pointed to instances where the various stakeholders are often working completely discretely without much regard for the work of other team members¹⁸.
- Early contractor involvement is not a feature of most construction projects, and can help to eliminate energy inefficiencies, first, by taking advantage of the contractors experience, and second, by ensuring that certain issues like draft proofing are not undone by poor sequencing of trades on site.
- Inability of the architect to be on site to communicate their vision.
- Not establishing the end-user requirements early enough in the project – if at all.
- Cooperation of building occupants during and after construction is often absent, but is decisive to establishing an appropriate energy saving occupant behaviour.

Public policy

- Lack of public sector funding to carry out projects that will lead by example
- Lack of enforcement of the polluter pays principle
- Heritage buildings are not only difficult to retrofit because of the many issues and trade-offs involved in reconciling the retrofit works with original and energy inefficient features and designs which must be kept for cultural reasons, but also because many of the grant incentives are based on compliance measures that are not achievable in such circumstances. Also, because heritage buildings are exempt from having to do the works in most cases, this disqualifies them for grants.
- Powerful lobbies have in the past been seen to obstruct progress in terms of the introduction of more energy efficient building materials and processes.

¹⁸ For example one respondent stated that as they were M&E engineers, and that glazing and insulation were a matter for the architects, and nothing to do with them – despite the fact that glazing and insulation specifications have quite a lot to do with the mechanical and electrical performance of the building

6.2 View from the Literature

The construction sector is a heterogeneous project-based industry delivered by transitory *ad hoc* business configurations characterised by intense price competition and often having short-term perspective (Dunphy *et al.* 2013). The sector’s project as opposed to process orientation and its short-termism means it typically not seen as innovative (Beerepoort 2007). This section comprises some views from the literature on energy efficiency innovation. UNEP SBCI (2009) contrast the built environment with other sectors associated with large quantities of GHG emissions. The construction sector is seen as having many small reduction opportunities spread across millions of buildings compared to the concentration of other sectors, in which there are large reduction potentials at a relatively small number of intervention points. As illustrated in Figure 4, it is relatively easy to achieve large emission reductions per unit in larger buildings; however it becomes increasingly difficult as buildings reduce in size. The large number of small buildings means that the aggregate savings from the “long tail” of smaller buildings is likely to exceed those from larger buildings.

Figure 4: Small savings from large numbers of end-use units constitute the long-tail distribution of building sector projects Source: Adapted from Hinostroza *et al.*, (2007), in UNEP SBCI (2009)

This means that the most substantial opportunities rest not with the ‘low-hanging fruit’ of large buildings, but rather with the far more inaccessible, risky, less profitable and fragmented market associated with smaller buildings. The nature of the opportunities in the long-tail conflicts with the nature of the building and construction sector, which Beerepoort (2007), characterises as closed, fragmented, conservative, and risk-averse. Buildings by their nature are long life complex products associated with complicated value chains involving multiple actors and stakeholders, all of whom impact on the buildings GHG emissions over its lifecycle. The sector is characterised by project-based *ad hoc* collaborations and fragmentation (Dunphy *et al.* 2013), which Faber and Hoppe (2013) see as hampering development of shared visions and integrated approaches, and fostering conservative attitudes and low levels of innovation. The long lifespan of buildings presents a problem in and of itself. While rational decision-making should dictate that energy efficiency measures

are costed over the full, expected lifetime of the buildings, this does not fit with the short-termism of many investment strategies. Furthermore, the lack of opportunities and incentives for these stakeholders to coordinate and the poor communication between decision makers in the design process and technology suppliers further inhibits adoption of new energy efficiency measures (UNEP SBCI 2009). This lack of communication also leads to poor understanding of, and response to, customer needs (Dougherty 1992). Perhaps the largest barrier to the adoption of energy efficiency measures in buildings is the perceived “first cost” barrier of measures and the relative limited time an occupant has to recover the cost. This issue is compounded by split incentives between stakeholders, for example in the case of rented properties: landlords who may not directly feel the cost of energy bills and have no incentive to invest in energy efficiency and tenants unwilling to make investments in energy saving features because they do not expect to use that property long enough to recoup their investment through energy savings. In the case of new builds similar divisions open up between the builders and future occupants (Faber & Hoppe 2013).

As energy costs are relatively low there are weak economic incentives to induce stakeholders to overcome the issue of these split incentives. This is especially the case where there is a perception amongst building professionals that energy efficiency measures add significantly to the overall costs of a building project (UNEP SBCI 2009). Segarra-Blasco *et al.* (2008) found that cost is the most significant barrier to innovation. The availability of finance for both companies and domestic households is seen as a significant barrier to increasing energy efficiency activity and the support innovation in the sector. This problem is particularly acute for low-income households, which often have limited access, and in many cases an aversion to, credit – creating difficulties in financing energy efficiency measures where benefits would only accrue in the long term. Faber and Hoppe (2013) see banks as reluctant to consider long-term investments (such as that required for energy efficient measures) and as being adverse to the risk of the unknown (*e.g.* funding innovation requiring further research and development). UNEP SBCI (2009) also report a lack of clear information on the performance of many existing buildings, which render difficult the determination of likely energy, financial and greenhouse savings’ that would accrue from a proposed energy efficiency intervention. This coupled with the low level of knowledge available on previous projects means that the transaction costs for acquiring relevant and complete information on applying energy-efficiency measures in housing (in particular) are often considered too high (Faber & Hoppe 2013).

Faber and Hoppe (2013) report a degree of technical lock-in, with Dutch construction work

primarily orientated towards carrying out routine work in a market with small profit margins and consequently with little incentive for exploring alternatives. This leads to the ‘chicken and egg’ scenario, where prospective clients complain about lack of innovative solutions from developers and on the other hand developers report little demand and therefore no perceived incentive for such innovation. Another issue relates to the legal protections granted to new inventions. The advantages and patent protection of inventions for the innovation process are questionable. The transactions costs associated with so-called intellectual property rights can act to retard scientific collaboration and to stifle innovation and market exploitation. Baca (2007) comments that *‘In an atmosphere of competition and secrecy, granting exclusive rights over upstream products will more likely lead to market shortages than to productive bargaining.’* Tiwari and Buse (2007) summarise the barriers to innovation in SMEs in Table 10 below, which offers a non-sector specific perspective on innovation, which is complementary to that focussed on issues particular to buildings.

Barriers to innovation in SMEs	Studies (amongst others)
Financial bottlenecks: hindered access to external finance; high innovation costs, high costs	Acs and Audretsch (1990), Baldwin and Gellatly (2003), Rammer <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Shortage of, and hindered access to qualified personnel	Ylinenpää (1998), FES (2004), Rammer <i>et al.</i> (2005), Rammer <i>et al.</i> (2006)
Limited internal know-how to manage the innovation process effectively and efficiently	Mohnen and Rosa (1999), Rammer <i>et al.</i> (2005), BMBF (2006)
Missing market knowledge	Ylinenpää (1998), FES (2004), HWWI (2004)
Bureaucratic hurdles: long administrative procedures; restrictive laws and regulations	Acs and Audretsch (1990), HWWI (2004), Rammer <i>et al.</i> (2006), BMBF (2006)
Lack of intellectual property rights	Baldwin and Gellatly (2003), BMBF (2006)

Table 10: Previous studies on barriers to Innovations in SMEs (after Tiwari & Buse 2007)

6.3 Lessons from policy development

López-Gamero *et al.* (2010) posit that policies, which are ‘command and control’ technology based standards, risk setting a maximum norm for performance and losing out of the capacity of the market to drive innovative processes – but on the other hand if they are not prescriptive enough, they run the risk of being ineffective. As discussed in section 4.3, there is a need to include both non-prescriptive approaches to stimulate strong innovation (*i.e.*, radical changes) in those who are beyond compliance, and more prescriptive approaches for require weak innovation (*i.e.*, incremental changes building on existing solutions) in less proactive actors (2012).

7 Recommendations

7.1 Conceptual context for recommendations

Klein Woolthuis *et al.* (2005) considered the imperfections found in innovation systems and building on previous work¹⁹, reframed the system failure framework, making a clear distinction between the ‘actors’ (who act to make policy objectives happen) and the ‘rules’ (the outcome of the actions) of the innovation system. They identified four types of systemic failures that occur within an innovation system, *viz.* infrastructure failures; institutional failures; interaction failures; and capabilities’ failure as illustrated in Figure 5.

Actors → ↓ Rules (system failures)	Demand <i>Consumers Large Buyers</i>	Companies <i>Multinationals SMEs</i>	Knowledge Institutes <i>Universities</i>	Third Parties <i>Banks, Consultants, Sector groups</i>
Infrastructure failure				
Institution failure: - Hard: laws, regulations, <i>etc</i> - Soft: norms, values, <i>etc.</i>				
Interaction failure: - Weak network Failure - Strong network Failure				
Capabilities’ failure				

Figure 5: System of innovation – policy framework (after Klein Woolthuis *et al.* 2005)

As mentioned above Klein Woolthuis *et al.* distinguish between the actors (which in addition to their other roles, co-create the framework in which they operate) and the rules (the operational context that has been created and/or evolved) of the innovation system. The rules are considered to be the area where system failures occur, while the actors through their actions either solve or create such failures. Klein Woolthuis *et al.* suggest that this allows users of the framework to differentiate between the cause and the effect of the systemic failures. Furthermore there discard the failure of lock-in, which is often presented as a barrier to innovation, is in fact the result of systemic failure rather than its cause. They go one step further and offer a definition for innovation system based policies as “the process of identifying the causes of lock-in and eliminating those bottlenecks to enable

¹⁹ including: Carlsson & Jacobsson (1997), Edquist (1997), Smith (1997), Malerba & Orsenigo (1997), Johnson & Gregersen (1994)

innovation and economic progress both as a firm and system level.”

Table 11: Overview of innovation system rules (after Klein Woolthuis et al. 2005)

Rules (system conditions)	Description
Infrastructure	This comprises both the physical (<i>e.g.</i> , information, communication & technology; energy supply; buildings, transportation systems <i>etc.</i>) and knowledge based (<i>e.g.</i> , scientific / engineering knowledge and skills, testing facilities, knowledge transfer processes, patents, education & training, <i>etc.</i>) infrastructure, which facilitate innovation activities
Institution	<p>‘Hard’ institutional rules refer to the formal institutional mechanisms that may hinder and/or support innovation <i>e.g.</i>, contract law, employment law, risk management rules, health and safety regulations, intellectual property rights, technical standards <i>etc.</i></p> <p>‘Soft’ institutional rules refer to the wider context of political context, societal values, and cultural norms which shape public policy objectives and the macroeconomic policy environment (Smith 1999).</p> <p>Klein Woolthuis <i>et al</i> (2005) suggest that ‘these institutions form the implicit rules of the game that can stimulate or hinder innovation’</p>
Interaction	Smith (1999) posits that a basic premise of the systems approach is that “market relationships persist through time and involve inter-firm cooperation in the development and design of products” Carlsson and Jacobsson (1997) distinguish between weak (too little interaction <i>e.g.</i> , poor communication between complementary actors) and strong (too much interaction, <i>e.g.</i> , perhaps dependence on a dominate partner) network failures which can both hinder innovation and lead to issues such as lock-in
Capabilities	This refers to competences, capacity, resources required to perform an expected role. Klein Woolthuis <i>et al</i> (2005) argue that for firms to move from an old to a new technology or paradigm requires “flexibility, learning potential, and resources to adapt to new technologies and market demands and be able to survive”

7.2 Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Policies should aim to develop new market opportunities not attempt to stimulate demand for particular technologies.

Relevant conditions: General;

Al-Saleh & Mahroum (2014) point out that the vast majority of policy instruments have focussed on stimulating the demand for more environmentally friendly technologies through the use of financial incentives. They suggest that this approach creates an artificial temporary demand, which often dissolves in the face of negative externalities such as opportunistic short-term profiteering. The business models that develop in response to this market opportunity tend to be focused on capturing and redistributing existing value rather than creating new value.

Recommendation 2: Alterations to innovation systems conditions (rules) should be done on a case-by-case basis with specific objectives in mind.

Relevant conditions: General

Governments should recognise that there is no one blueprint for the governance of (technology) innovation systems and that any attempts to develop such a universal approach would be misplaced (Winkel *et al.* 2014).

Recommendation 3: A multi-perspective view should be taken to while improving innovation governance.

Relevant conditions: General

The different conceptual innovation systems – national, regional, sectoral, technical – should not be considered as mutually exclusive rather as different perspectives into the innovation process. To deliver effective enhancements to the innovation conditions (rules) it will be necessary to consider the impact of changes from the perspectives of multiple system views. For example governments should recognise the transnational dimension in planning support for technology innovation systems *i.e.*, accept that countries do not have to have strengths in all aspects of a innovation value chain (Gosens *et al.* 2014)

Recommendation 4: *The concept of innovation needs to be reframed in recognition that not all innovation is technological.*

Relevant conditions: General

This is a need to acknowledge that innovation can also be non-technological e.g., improvement in ways of doing business (i.e., business models). Furthermore even technological innovation may require enabling sociological changes Fri and Savitz (2014) that the adoption of cost-effective energy efficient technologies is ‘affected as much by individual choice, preference, and behaviour as by technological performance’.

Recommendation 5: *Industry led partnerships should complement but not replace stakeholder engagement in the policy making process.*

Relevant conditions: Institutional

Winkel *et al.* (2014) recognise a great risk that public policy will be captured by incumbent interests. For example Diedrich *et al.* (2011) argues that industry led partnerships such as the European Technology Platforms have become ‘disproportionally shaped by larger companies’ and that smaller enterprises and non-governmental organisations do not have the capacity to develop or even contribute to a research agenda.

Recommendation 6: *Greater efforts need to be made to include the views of smaller companies and non-governmental organisations in policy development.*

Relevant conditions: Institutional; Interaction

The lack of participation from SMEs, which often are the source of radical ideas, can result in policy developments that stifle strong innovation, for example Faber and Hoppe (2013) note that where radical innovation takes place, smaller enterprises tend to be more involved in process innovation, while larger firms have a stronger track record in incremental product innovation.

Recommendation 7: Support project-based knowledge capture initiatives and develop inter-firm knowledge exchanges for energy efficiency building activity

Relevant conditions: Interaction; Capability

Emtairah *et al.* (2008) note knowledge gained during a construction project is rarely documented and consequently lost following its completion. This lack of organisational learning is a significant impediment to innovation.

Recommendation 8: Review education and training of building professional for applicability to an enhanced focus on energy efficiency retrofits

Relevant conditions: Institution; Capability

This skills shortage is seen as one of the most significant barriers (along with lack of finance) to innovation generally (Segarra-Blasco *et al.* 2008) and to energy efficiency projects specifically (UNEP SBCI 2009; Tiwari & Buse 2007).

Recommendation 9: Facilitate and promote the development of financial approaches that decouple project funding from owners' ability to get credit.

Relevant conditions: Capability; Institution; Interaction

Development of innovative approaches such as: pay-as-you-save *e.g.* some aspects of the Green Deal in the UK, revolving community investment funds; targeted property taxation schemes *e.g.*, PACE – property assessed clean energy in the US; aggregation of properties and projects for funding purposes.

Recommendation 10: Optimise policy mix to encourage building energy front-runners as well as laggards.

Relevant conditions: Institution

As discussed earlier, Williamson and Lynch-Wood (2012) see a need for different types of policy instruments to bring about environmental improvements by both actors which occupy ‘beyond compliance’ positions and those who may be performance laggards.

Recommendation 11: Review of existing policies for coherence.

Relevant conditions: Institution

Very often there are policies which work at cross-purposes to each other or at the very least reduce the effectiveness of each other. Faber & Hoppe give the example of a conflicting regulatory framework, where local taxes are determined in relation to house value, determined annually by the local council. Investments in energy performance appliances through renovation would increase house value leading to higher local taxes, and so disincentivising owners from making such an investment.

Recommendation 12: Review of existing policy instruments for applicability to current objectives.

Relevant conditions: Institution

Beerepoot & Beerepoot (2007) question if regulations target the most appropriate part of the building value chain and pose the question – would it be more effective to target technology manufacturers rather than construction contractors?

8 References

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Appendix I – Policies relevant to energy efficient building projects

I-1. Kingdom of Spain

I-1.1. Normative policy instruments, Spain (S-N)

S-N-01 Spanish Building Regulations

Spain has 17 Autonomous Communities, c. 8,000 Local Authorities, and 52 Provinces. Ley 38/1999, de 5 de noviembre, de Ordenación de la Edificación (Spanish Planning and Building Law).

Related documents – The Spanish ‘Recognised Documents’ / Documentos Basicos

S-N-02 Regulation on Indoor Heating and Air-conditioning Systems (RITE)

The Regulation on Indoor Heating and Air-conditioning Systems (RITE), promulgated by the Royal Decree 1027/2007 of 20 July 2007, came into force on 29 February 2008 after revision. The Regulation forms the basic legislative framework laying down the energy efficiency and safety requirements to be met by heating and cooling systems in buildings, with a view to meeting comfort and hygiene demands, during their design, construction, maintenance and use. It also specifies compliance procedures. The approval of this Regulation implies an advance in the transposing of the Directive 2002/91/EC on the energy performance of buildings, setting minimum energy efficiency requirements to be met by thermal systems in new and existing buildings and a procedure for the periodic inspection of boilers and air conditioning systems. The more stringent energy efficiency requirements laid down in RITE 2007 are:

- Improved energy performance of heating and cooling equipment, and of equipment designed to transport fluids;
- Improved insulation of heat transport equipment, pipes and fluids;
- Better regulation and control to maintain the design conditions envisaged in air-conditioned premises;
- Use of available renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy and biomass;
- Incorporation of subsystems for heat recovery and utilisation of residual energy;
- Mandatory metering systems for consumption for collective systems;
- Gradual elimination of more polluting solid fuels;
- Gradual elimination of less efficient generating equipment.

This Regulation also forms one of the development programmes within the Energy Saving and Efficiency Plan, and will also help to achieve the objectives laid down by the Renewable Energy Promotion Plan, by encouraging greater use of solar thermal energy, particularly in the production of domestic hot water.

S-N-03 Implementation of the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive

The EU Energy Performance in Buildings Directive began implementation in Spain for new buildings (and major renovations) on 30 October 2007. Software tools were developed and distributed free of charge for residential and small business buildings as well as for large tertiary buildings. In addition, a simplified certification methodology for residential buildings was approved by Royal Decree 47/2007 on 19 January 2007. In the course of 2007 several regulations were passed on the energy efficiency of buildings, notably the Building Energy Certification (CER) and the Regulations on Building Heating Installations (RITE), approved by Royal Decrees RD 47/2007 and RD 1027/2007 respectively. These approvals together with the Technical Building Code (TBC) contribute to the partial transposition of the Directive 2002/91/EC on the energy efficiency of buildings into the Spanish legislation.

The TBC includes a Basic Energy Saving Document and covers regulations on: limitations on energy demand (heating and air-conditioning); performance of Thermal Installations/Air-conditioning systems; efficiency in the indoor lighting installations; minimum solar thermal contribution (hot water), and minimum PV contribution.

S-N-04 Technical Building Code (TBC), Royal Decree 314/2006

The TBC is the regulatory framework that establishes the demands to be met by buildings in terms of the basic security and living conditions requirements. It contains a free Energy Saving Document with the basic requirements set out in energy efficiency and renewable energy that must be met in new buildings and interventions in existing buildings.

S-N-05 Regulations on Building Heating Installations (RITE), consolidated version of the Royal Decree 1027/2007

RITE provides regulations about the energy efficiency and security of thermal installations relative to heating, cooling, ventilation and sanitary hot water. It also makes the periodic energy efficiency inspection obligatory for installations that are over 15 years old.

I-1.2. Mandatory Informative policy instruments, Spain (S-MI)

S-MI-01 Building Energy Certification

In order to comply with the Directive 93/76/EC and improve the energy efficiency of buildings, in 1999 the General Directorate for Housing, Architecture and Urbanism of the Ministry of Public Works and Urbanism (Dirección General para la Vivienda, la Arquitectura y el Urbanismo del Ministerio de Fomento) and the Institute for the Diversification and Saving of Energy (Instituto para la

Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía, IDAE) signed a collaboration agreement to carry out an energy certification programme for buildings, which, at first, would focus on residential housing and then cover all types of buildings. The requirement for certification of buildings in the EU Directive on the energy performance of buildings was partly transposed in January 2007 by Royal Decree 47/2007, outlining the procedure for the energy certification of new buildings. As of 1 November 2007, an Energy Performance Certificate must be provided to buyers or renters of buildings. The Royal Decree established a register of technical documents recognised for the energy certification of buildings, according to requirements outlined by the Ministry of Industry and the Ministry of Housing. Building on the procedure in the Royal Decree, Regional Governments will develop specific procedures, as well as register certificates and undertake inspections. The computer application for the previous energy certification of buildings programme has been updated according to the Royal Decree 47/2007 and is available free of charge in the web site of the Ministry of Industry, Tourism and Trade.

Royal Decree 235/2013 (Certification of energy efficiency of buildings) establishes the obligation to make available to the buyers or users of buildings energy performance certificate, which must include factual information about the energy efficiency of a building and reference values such as minimum energy requirements. This will enable potential buyers and users to easily evaluate and compare the energy performance of buildings, thus promoting energy-efficient buildings and energy saving investments.

S-MI-02 Certification Programmes for RES installations

This is an obligatory certification for solar thermal panels to comply with international standards UNE-EN 12975 and UNE-EN 12976. Specifically, UNE-EN 12975 applies to solar panels with liquid cooling systems and UNE-EN 12976 applies to prefabricated thermal solar panels.

S-MI-03 Energy Certification of Buildings, Royal Decree 235/2013 (update of Royal Decree 47/2007)

Energy efficiency certification procedure for existing buildings: it is the transposition of Directive 2010/31/EU that sets out the Energy Performance Certification (EPC).

I-1.3. Market based policy instruments, Spain (S-MB)

S-MB-01 Savings and energy efficiency programme in business

This financial programme aims to promote investments in high energy-efficient rating installations in companies to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions.

S-MB-02 Savings and energy efficiency programme in energy transformation sector – Valencia

This financial programme aims to promote the uptake of co-generation installations.

S-MB-03 Savings and energy efficiency programme in public sector – Valencia

This financial programme aims to promote improvements of public lighting plants into more energy efficient ones.

S-MB-04 Renewable Energy and Biofuel Programme – Valencia

This financial programme aims to promote renewable energy take up and use of biofuels.

I-1.4. Fiscal policy instruments, Spain (S-F)

S-F-01 PAREER Programme (Aid Programme for Energy Rehabilitation in Buildings in the Household and Hotel Sectors) (October 2013 - October 2015)

This is a financing programme for energy retrofitting of residential buildings. It aims to promote comprehensive actions favouring energy efficiency improvement and the use of renewable energies in the housing stock of existing buildings in the residential sector. To benefit from it, actions must fit with one the following:

- Improvement of the thermal envelope energy efficiency;
- Improvement of energy efficiency in thermal and lighting installations;
- Replacement of conventional energy with biomass in thermal installations;
- Replacement of conventional energy with geothermal energy in thermal installations.

S-F-02 JESSICA-F.I.D.A.E. funding (Andalusia, Canary Islands, Castile and Leon, Castile-La Mancha, Ceuta, Valencian Community, Extremadura, Galicia, Melilla, Murcia)

This programme finances sustainable urban development projects that aim to improve energy efficiency or use renewable energy.

S-F-03 BIOMCASA II Programme

This programme aims to promote and finance thermal biomass projects in Spain. Companies are incorporated in the programme. This aims to finance authorised companies for biomass installations in buildings.

S-F-04 GEOTCASA Programme

This programme means to set up a financing system to boost a quality offer adapted to users' needs for hot water, heating and cooling in buildings using geothermal energy. Consumers must call on authorised firms services.

S-F-05 SOLCASA Programme

This programme means to set up a financing system to boost a quality offer adapted to users' needs for hot water, heating and cooling in buildings using solar thermal energy. Consumers must call on authorised firms services.

S-F-06 GIT Programme

This offers financing to authorised firms for Large Thermal Installations running on renewable energies in the building sector. The launching of this financing programme responds to the need to boost the implementation of large installations to produce thermal energy in building from the exploitation of renewable energies such as biomass, solar thermal and geothermal energy.

S-F-07 Project Finance and Provision of Service

This programme is a form of financial cooperation in which IDAE provides advisory and coordination services and the finance for an investment project.

S-F-08 RENOVE Tourism Plan 2009

This financial plan offers loans for energy efficiency projects.

S-F-09 Savings and energy efficiency Programme in Building sector – Valencia

This programme aims to reduce the energy consumption of thermal installations and lighting in buildings by promoting newly built buildings with high-energy ratings. This programme provides part of the project investment, without the need to pay it off.

S-F-10 Energy Diversification Programme

This financial programme aims to promote the substitution of oil products with natural gas for companies in any economic sector or public sector.

S-F-11 Premium tariff (Régimen retributivo específico)

The “Specific scheme” is not technically defined as a support scheme, but as a complementary retribution to allow renewable technologies to compete with traditional technologies in the energy market.

The specific amounts will be based on a number of parameters, each calculated for a set of “standard installations”. The rationale behind the scheme is to provide developers an amount based on the “reasonable rentability” that a well-managed renewable plant would have. In order to determine such costs and

values, a set of theoretical standard installations has been developed and their values calculated. Furthermore, these values are linked to the “reasonable rentability”, defined as the average yield of the State obligations to ten years in the secondary market for the 24 months prior to the month of May of the year preceding the start of the regulatory period increased by a spread (art. 19 RD 413/2014). On the basis of these results, an actual plant would receive the amount that its correspondent well-managed theoretical standard installation would receive. All technologies participating in the electricity market are eligible (Art. 11.1 RD 413/2014)

S-F-12 Grants for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

The minimum energy efficiency requirements for buildings are included in Royal Decree 314/2006 (Technical Building Code) Royal Decree 47/2007 (Building Energy Certification) and Royal Decree 1027/2007 (Regulations on Building Heating Installations - RITE). These regulations are mandatory. Additional improvements are in some case granted through several economic support lines managed by IDAE and the Autonomous Regions governments. In December 2007, the Spanish government announced that it would provide EUR 1 billion worth of subsidies for the refurbishment of existing residential buildings between 2008 and 2012, together with EUR 2 billion in credit for energy efficiency improvements to homes. Additionally, the government announced it would provide EUR 200 million for energy efficiency improvements to schools and public buildings in large towns and cities.

S-F-13 Energy renewal of the thermal envelope in existing buildings

This measure aims to promote the energy renewal of the thermal envelope (as a whole or partially) in existing buildings to reduce the energy demand in heating and cooling, so the buildings will comply with and improve the minimum requirements set out by the Technical Building Code. This measure includes action mechanisms: regulatory, financial incentives, training and information.

I-1.5. Support policy instruments, Spain (S-S)

S-S-01 Improved energy efficiency of thermal installations in existing buildings

This measure aims to improve the energy efficiency of thermal installation for heating, climate control and the production of sanitary hot water, reducing their consumption. Actions taken will have to make the installations comply with the requirements set out in the Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings (RITE) and other regulations in force in the field. This measure includes action mechanisms: regulatory, financial incentives, training, information and market inspection.

- S-S-02 Improved energy efficiency of interior lighting plants in existing buildings*
- This measure aims to improve the energy efficiency of interior lighting installations in existing buildings, reducing their energy consumption. The renewals will have to comply with and improve upon the minimum requirements set out in the Technical Building Code. This measure includes action mechanisms: regulatory, financial incentives, training and information.
- S-S-03 Construction of new buildings and renewal of existing buildings with high energy rating*
- This measure aims to reduce energy consumption through the promotion of newly built buildings or renewal of existing ones, with high energy ratings. Through these measures, the affected buildings will have to achieve a class A or B energy rating to comply with that set out in Royal Decree 47/2007 and the regional regulations applicable in the field. This measure includes action mechanisms: regulatory, financial incentives, training, information and market inspection.
- S-S-04 Construction or renewal of buildings with practically nearly zero energy consumption*
- This measure aims to promote the construction of buildings with almost zero energy consumption. This measure meets the expectation of the Directive 2010/31/EU. The measure includes action mechanisms: financial incentives and communication.
- S-S-05 Improved energy efficiency in cold commercial plants*
- This measure aims to promote improved energy efficiency of existing cold commercial plants that have been renewed, reducing their energy consumption. The measure includes action mechanisms: financial incentives and information.
- S-S-06 Improved energy efficiency of electrical appliances*
- This measure aims to reduce energy consumption through the improved energy efficiency of electrical appliances or, more generally, energy-consuming electrical appliances. It encourages buyers to replace their appliances with another with a better energy rating, through a financial incentive. The measure includes action mechanisms: regulatory, financial incentives, training and information.
- S-S-07 Guide: "How to save energy installing home automation at home. Gain comfort and security"*
- This guide is aimed at all citizens to let them know how home automation can contribute to saving energy and promoting responsible energy consumption.

- S-S-08 Guide: "Practical energy guide for building refurbishment. Insulation, the best solution" and Technical guides on insulation materials"*
- The first guide is a dissemination guide aimed at every user of residential properties. The second guide supplements the general information provided in the first one; it is a series of practical guides focussing on each type of insulating material and is aimed at the professional sector.
- S-S-09 URSOS Programme, sustainable town planning*
- This programme is a software application. Thanks to it, persons in charge of town planning can evaluate the sustainability of the environment for a building or retrofit project.
- S-S-10 Network of Spanish Cities for Climate (RECC, Red Española de Ciudades por el Clima)*
- This network is the section of the Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP) that unites cities and towns committed to sustainable development and the protection of the climate. Its aim is to become a technical support instrument for these local corporations, offering them the tools required to achieve sustainable development. The central themes of the network's interventions are energy efficiency and the development of renewable energy, bioclimatic architecture and sustainable town planning.
- S-S-11 RD&D Policies (National plan of scientific research, development and technological innovation 2013 - 2016)*
- This plan is the programming instrument that establishes goals and priorities of the national research policy in the mid-term. The plan covers very different areas and topics. One of its strategic actions is "Reliable, safe and clean energy". Within this strategic action, a number of priority areas of intervention are considered: Solar Energy (thermal, PV, thermoelectric); Wind Energy; Bio Energy; Waste treatment with energy goals; Hydrogen and fuel cells; Sea and Tidal energy; Geothermal; Sustainable nuclear power; Carbon Capture and Storage; Smart grids.
- S-S-12 Training programmes for installers (National system of qualification and professional formation)*
- The national system of qualification and professional formation (NSQPF) provides a structured framework for the provision of vocational training in 26 different professional areas, among which "energy" is also considered. Within this area, the following certifications are listed, along with the training requirements necessary for their achievement:
- Installation and maintaining of PV facilities;

- Installation and maintaining of solar thermal facilities;
- Installation and maintaining management of wind parks.

INCUAL (the National Qualifications Institute, a technical instrument of the General Council of Vocational Education and Training) elaborates and actualises the national catalogue of professional qualifications. On the basis of this catalogue, courses aimed at reaching those qualifications are offered and developed by the Ministry of Education or the local authorities, as confirmed by INCUAL.

S-S-13 National Energy Plan 2008-16

A national energy plan to 2016 was announced in May 2008. The plan predicts an annual growth of 1.4 per cent in energy demand. The plan allots an investment of EUR 9.22 m in improving electrical infrastructure and of EUR 10.2 m in gas infrastructure. It calls for increased energy production capacity and diversifying the energy mix, by increasing wind- and gas-fired capacity and a reduction in other fossil fuel and nuclear generation. Extra effort to support renewables is also promised.

S-S-14 Spanish Strategy on Climate Change and Clean Energy Horizon 2007-2012-2020

The Spanish Climate Change and Clean Energy Strategy aims to reach an effective emission reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, related to energy and the accomplishment of Kyoto targets. In terms of Clean Energy, various objectives and measures are outlined, through four lines of action for energy efficiency, renewable energy, demand management, and research development and innovation. All of these call for the creation of new financing mechanisms. In energy efficiency, the strategy seeks to ensure efficiency improvements are beneficial overall, by removing fare structures that encourage consumption, and putting in place regulatory measures to prevent increased demand for energy should efficiency lead to reduced energy costs.

S-S-15 RIVA Rehabilitation of Valencia – Valencia

Best practice guidelines for development and rehabilitation of the historical centre of Valencia. (Related to the Valencian Local Authority Development plan)

S-S-16 Saving & Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2011-2020, 2nd National Energy Efficiency Action Plan in Spain

National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAP) under the Energy Services Directive (2006/32/EC)

S-S-17 Spanish Energy Efficiency Strategy (E4) 2004-2012

The Spanish Energy Efficiency Strategy 2004-2012 was a policy strategy presented by the Government in November 2003 and approved by the Parliament in December 2003. The strategy involves saving energy resources and limiting external dependency by environmental improvements. The strategy is integrated in the process definition of the new Spanish energy frame, and gathers the actions of multiple stakeholders in search of a common objective: the reduction in the energy intensity in Spain by about 7.2% through 2004-2012. The following sectors have been considered in the Strategy: Energy Transformation; Transport; Buildings; Tertiary, Residential and Public Services; Industry; Agriculture.

I-2. United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

I-2.1. Normative policy instruments, United Kingdom (UK-N)

UK-N-01 Zero Carbon Homes and Building Regulation

All new homes need to be zero carbon from 2016 and all new non-domestic buildings from 2019. The new building regulations improve basic performance standards on fuel and energy conservation for all new buildings.

UK-N-02 PAS (Publicly Available Specification) 2030

In the context of the Green Deal: all energy efficiency measures, financed under a Green Deal, must be installed in full accordance with these specifications.

UK-N-03 Building Standards – Scotland

Defined by the Building Standards Division, building standards include energy standards that are often reviewed (every three years since 2007 until 2016). The Technical Handbooks provide guidance on achieving the standards set in the Building (Scotland) Regulations 2004 and are available in two volumes, Domestic buildings and Non-domestic buildings, last updated in 2013. Both Technical Handbooks are divided into 8 parts as follows: General; Structure; Fire; Environment; Safety; Noise; Energy; Sustainability.

UK-N-04 Scottish Housing Quality Standard – Scotland

The Scottish Housing Quality Standard (SHQS) was introduced in February 2004 and is the Scottish Government's principal measure of housing quality in Scotland. The purpose of introducing a minimum housing standard in Scotland is essentially to provide a 'floor' below which a property should ideally not fall. In the case of the social housing sector (local authority landlords and Registered Social Landlords), Scottish Government has set a policy target for those landlords

to bring their stock up to every element of the standard (where applicable) by April 2015. Other public sector landlords, for example university accommodation and the Ministry of Defence are not subject to that policy target. Private sector landlords and owner-occupied households in Scotland are not subject to the April 2015 policy target either but each property can still be assessed against SHQS if required for whatever reason.

UK-N-05 *Construction products regulations & CE marking*

The European Construction Products Directive (89/106/EEC), which seeks to remove technical barriers to the trade of construction products. Under the CPR, from 1 July 2013 a construction product will need to be CE marked and accompanied by a declaration of performance if it is to be placed on the market in the European Economic Area and it is covered by a harmonised European product standard or a European technical assessment. (These are used by manufacturers of products, which are not covered by a harmonised European standard but who still wish their products to be CE marked). The CPR aims to ensure the reliability of information on the performance of such products. This is achieved through harmonised European product standards and European Technical Assessments using a common technical language and uniform assessment methods. The scope of the CPR and associated CE marking is limited to product characteristics for which there are national provisions relating to the products' use under the following headings: (1) Mechanical resistance and stability; (2) Safety in case of fire; (3) Hygiene, health and the environment; (4) Safety and accessibility in use; (5) Protection against noise; (6) Energy economy and heat retention; (7) Sustainable use of natural resources.

I-2.2. Mandatory informative policies, United Kingdom (UK-MI)

UK-MI-01 *Mandatory Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Reporting Scheme*

All UK stock exchange listed companies²⁰ have to report on their GHG emissions, including from energy use. As a result, investors will be able to see which companies are effectively managing the long-term cost of GHG emissions.

UK-MI-02 *Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) – EU*

This A-G rating scheme must be provided to any buyer or tenant of a property constructed, sold or rented out. This document states the energy efficiency of the concerned building.

²⁰ UK incorporated companies that are listed on the main market of the London Stock Exchange, on a stock exchange elsewhere in the European Economic Area, or that have been admitted to dealing on NASDAQ or the New York Stock Exchange

UK-MI-03 Certification Programmes for RES installations (Microgeneration Certification Scheme)

The Microgeneration Certification Scheme (MCS) is aimed at providing an assessment and an approval that a RES installation complies with specific standards. The scheme covers electricity generating technologies with a capacity of up to 50kW as well as heat generating technologies with a capacity of up to 45kW. MCS is linked to Government's financial support schemes. Thus to access support under FiT scheme or Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) scheme, both the installed product and the installation company must be MCS certified. For accreditation various European and International standards have to be met. Standards depend on the technology.

MCS is an industry-led and internationally recognised quality insurance scheme, supported by DECC. It certifies microgeneretaion products used to produce electricity and heat from renewable sources. It also certifies installation companies to ensure the products installation has been done under the highest standard for the consumer. It covers technologies with a capacity up to 50kW (electricity) or up to 45kW (heat).

UK-MI-04 Feed-in Tariffs (FITs)

The scheme encourages deployment of additional small-scale low-carbon electricity generation. People who have invested in such installations will obtain a guaranteed payment from electricity suppliers for the electricity they generate or export back to the grid in case of unused surplus.

The feed-in tariff (FiT) system (England, Wales and Scotland) aims to support small-scale RES-E plants (less than 5 MW, however plants between 50 kW and 5 MW located in Great Britain are entitled to choose between this system and the quota system "Renewables Obligation" – art. 17B, 17D ROO 2009 in conjunction with art. 3 FTO 2012). Plants using eligible sources must undergo an accreditation process, which may differ according to plant size and energy source. Once this process is completed and a plant has been accredited, the electricity exported to the grid by the plant is bought by a FiT licensee, i.e. an electricity supplier, at the rates fixed by the FTO 2012 and corrected yearly by the Gas and Electricity Markets Authority (Ofgem).

I-2.3. UK Market based policy instruments (U-MB)

UK-MB-01 Government Buying Standards (GBS)

Easy-to-use product specifications enable public authorities to develop tenders that procure sustainably. There are around 50 standards in a range of product areas of construction and construction products or transport.

UK-MB-02 Energy Company Obligation (ECO)

This policy replaces the previous Carbon Emission Reduction Target (CERT) and Community Energy Saving Programme (CESP) funding. In addition to Green Deal finance, this helps most vulnerable consumers and hard-to-treat homes. Energy suppliers must deliver energy efficiency measures to domestic energy users.

I-2.4. UK Fiscal policies (UK-F)

UK-F-01 Landlord's Energy Saving Allowance (LESA)

People can obtain LESA and reduce their tax bill by up to GBP 1,500 a year for the cost of buying and installing energy-saving products for properties they rent out like cavity wall and loft insulation or hot water system insulation.

UK-F-02 Home renewable loans Scheme – Scotland

Homeowners can benefit from a loan from the Scottish Government if they want to install a domestic renewable system or to connect to a renewably powered district-heating scheme. Up to 75% of the total cost up to 10,000 for a renewable system or up to 100% of the total cost up to GBP 5,000 for the connection to an approved district-heating scheme.

UK-F-03 Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

All large companies in the UK will have to undertake energy audit by 2015 and every 4 years thereafter. As a result, they will be able to identify the most cost-effective energy efficiency opportunities. It ensures businesses will be better informed, but there is no obligation to make improvements.

UK-F-04 Tax regulation mechanism (Carbon Price Floor)

The Carbon Price Floor (CPF) is a tax levied on fossil fuels, applied in Great Britain from April 2013. The carbon price support rates of the Climate Change Levy are applied to gas, solid fuels and liquefied petroleum gas that are used for electricity generation. Electricity from renewable sources is exempt from this tax.

UK-F-05 Climate Change Levy (CCL)

Tax on energy use in industry, commerce and public sectors, used to support energy efficiency and renewables. The CCL applies to industry, commerce, agriculture and public services, but not to small businesses using little energy, domestic users, and charities.

UK-F-06 The Green Deal

This is a financing framework launched by the UK government to help people make energy efficiency improvements to buildings. The scheme's applicants avoid the upfront costs, which are covered by a loan. Properties make energy

efficiency improvements and pay it back with the money saved on their energy bills. The loan is connected to the properties, so in case of an occupant change, it will be transferred to the next bill payer. A non-domestic Green Deal also exists.

UK-F-07 Green Deal Communities Scheme

DECC is inviting local authorities (LAs), working with their local partners, to apply for funds of between GBP 1-3m to help drive Green Deal energy efficiency improvements in their area. LAs are asked to come forward with ambitious and innovative proposals to deliver Green Deal Plans to as many properties as possible in target streets/areas. DECC funding can also be used to support those who choose to self-finance measures. Proposals which seek to reach areas, which have not benefited under previous schemes are particularly welcome. Proposals will be judged on:

- the number and total value of Green Deal Plans that will be delivered;
- their sustainability in the long term (*i.e.*, beyond the DECC funding);
- their credibility *e.g.*, LAs will need to demonstrate that they have secured ECO funding to complement Green Deal Plans under their Green Deal Communities bid, and to have specifically identified the streets/areas targeted;
- their creativity in offering local incentives to drive demand for Green Deal Plans;
- consistency with state aid and procurement rules.

UK-F-08 Renewable Heating Incentive (RHI)

It is a financial incentive scheme designed to encourage uptake of renewable heating. It provides long-term financial support to big renewable heat installations in industrial and business sectors and the public sector.

UK-F-09 Renewable Heat Premium Payment (RHPP) for households

RHPP is like RHI but it is aimed at the household sector (small renewable heat installations, for private owners) whereas RHI is intended for industrial, business and public sectors. RHPP is less important because there is less money invested

UK-F-10 Central Energy Efficiency Fund – Scotland

It is a key vehicle for delivering energy efficiency measures and small-scale renewable energy take-up across the public sector. In 2004, the Scottish Government announced the launch of a new Public Sector Energy Efficiency Initiative. Under this initiative, GBP 20 million in new funding was provided over 2004/05 and 2005/06 to implement energy efficiency and, from 2008, renewable energy measures, to reduce carbon emissions across the public sector in Scotland. The scheme applies to all Scottish local authorities and health boards as well as Scottish Water.

I-2.5. Support

UK-S-01 UK Green Investment Bank

The bank support private investment in energy efficiency projects and stimulate take up. Their business model is as follows:

- They are an investor in UK based green infrastructure projects;
- They primarily invest in three sectors, energy efficiency, waste and bioenergy and offshore wind;
- Each investment must offer returns against their green and financial double bottom line - it must make a positive contribution to the banks five green purposes and it must provide commercial returns in line with the project's risk;
- They invest on terms equivalent to others in the market - they do not offer low cost finance or grants;
- They work to mobilise other private sector capital, crowding in additional finance rather than displacing other investors; and are committed to being innovative by building and strengthening the UK market not simply serving it.

UK-S-02 Smart Metering

It is an objective to have a smart meter in every UK home by 2019.

UK-S-03 Government action to help hardworking people with energy bills

Grants are given to people buying a house in which they want to make energy efficiency improvements. Up to GBP 1,000 for important energy-saving measures and up to GBP 4,000 for particularly expensive measure. The scheme is worth GBP 540 million over 3 years, to boost energy efficiency for home-movers, landlords and public sector buildings.

UK-S-04 Energy Saving Advice Service

The Service provides households with impartial advice about energy efficiency measures. It also provides advice about policies available like Green Deal or RHI

Telephone advice service run by Energy Saving Trust for homes and businesses (it is not commercial, it offers impartial energy-saving advice).

UK-S-05 Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland (HEEPS): ex-EAP (Energy Assistance Package) – Scotland

HEEPS is a national scheme designed to provide measures to help people likely to have difficulty paying their energy bills or keeping their home sufficiently warm. It aims to tackle fuel poverty and improve energy efficiency in homes. It includes several schemes (listed below). It also provides a free home energy check before taking up any measure.

- HEEPS Affordable Warmth Scheme – Scotland. Energy companies/suppliers may offer energy efficiency measures to households like heating systems or insulation to make home warmer and cheaper to heat.
- HEEPS Energy Assistance Scheme – Scotland. This scheme is aimed at those who are most vulnerable to fuel poverty. The Scottish government partially finances energy efficiency measures for households like heating systems or insulation to make the home more energy efficient.
- HEEPS Area Based Schemes (ABS) – Scotland (different in each area). The Government works with Local Authorities to help finance energy efficiency improvements to cut the energy bills making homes warmer and cheaper to warm.

UK-S-06 House Energy Efficiency Learning Network – Scotland

This network provides advice to organisations and to individuals working in the housing sector. The Housing Energy Efficiency Learning Network is a cross-Government initiative that supports housing associations and co-operatives, local authorities and developers to provide more energy efficient housing. The network gives practical help to organisations and individuals working at a local level.

UK-S-07 Energy and Resource Efficiency Service – Scotland

This service provides energy efficiency advices to businesses of all size in Scotland. It is a ‘virtual one stop’ service where organisations in Scotland can more easily receive accurate, relevant advice and support on energy and resource efficiency issues affecting their business.

UK-S-08 Training programmes for Installers (Green Deal Skills Alliance)

The Green Deal Skills Alliance (GDSA) was launched in January 2012 by DECC. Its aim is to ensure that the UK has the right skills to implement the Green Deal - the flagship policy to improve the energy efficiency of buildings. GDSA is tasked with creating new training and accreditation opportunities for the energy assessment, advice and installation workforce.

UK-S-09 Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)

EDR aims to incentivise businesses to install measures that deliver verifiable reduction in demand by offering them financial incentives.

The Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) Project was initiated in 2011 to fulfil a commitment made within the Electricity Market Reform White Paper, to assess whether there is sufficient support and incentives available for households, businesses and organisations to use electricity more efficiently.

UK-S-10 OCRC (Carbon Reduction Commitment) Energy Efficiency Scheme

This scheme targets emissions not already covered by Climate Change Agreements and the EU Emissions Trading System. It affects large public and private sector (e.g. supermarkets, water companies, banks, local authorities). Designed to improve energy efficiency and cut emissions, it features a range of drivers to encourage participants to develop energy management strategies.

UK-S-11 The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)

The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO) supports the government's policy on reducing greenhouse gas emissions from vehicles by encouraging the production of biofuels that don't damage the environment. Under the RTFO suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources. Fuel suppliers who supply at least 450,000 litres of fuel a year are affected. This includes suppliers of biofuels as well as suppliers of fossil fuel.

UK-S-12 Five-year Carbon-Budgets

Beginning in 2008, each five-year period provide a transitional target to reach the 2050 target of Greenhouse Gas emissions (2050 target = reducing UK emissions by 80% on 1990 baseline).

UK-S-13 The National Energy Efficiency Data-Framework (NEED)

The National Energy Efficiency Data-Framework (NEED) was set up by DECC to provide a better understanding of energy use and energy efficiency in domestic and non-domestic buildings in Great Britain. The data framework matches gas and electricity consumption data, collected for DECC sub-national energy consumption statistics, with information on energy efficiency measures installed in homes, from the Homes Energy Efficiency Database (HEED). It also includes data about property attributes and household characteristics, obtained from a range of sources.

UK-S-14 Helping Households to cut their energy bills

This is a policy of the Department of Energy and Climate Change and the Minister of State for Climate Change and others to help householders with their energy bills. DECC has launched the following initiatives to help increase energy efficiency in households so consumers can save money on their energy bills:

- Green Deal – lets homes and businesses make energy efficiency improvements with some or all of the cost paid for from the savings on their energy bills;

- Smart meters – a programme to install gas and electricity meters that provide near real-time information on energy use in households and small businesses;
- The Energy Company Obligation (ECO) – a subsidy from energy suppliers that will work alongside the Green Deal to provide energy-saving home improvements for those most in need and for properties that are harder to treat;
- Electricity Demand Reduction project – assesses whether there is sufficient support and incentives to households, businesses and organisations to improve the efficiency of their electricity use;
- Smarter Heating Controls Research Programme - to establish whether ‘smarter’ heating controls reduce domestic energy consumption.

UK-S-15 Greening Government Commitments

This scheme targets a 25% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions from central government estate by 2015 (2009/2010 baseline). The Greening Government Commitments (GGCs) are targets for reducing the environmental impact of government estates and operations over the lifetime of this Parliament.

The second annual report of progress against the GGCs in 2012 to 2013 is intended for stakeholders in both the public and private sectors and individual citizens, to demonstrate transparently that government departments in England and their arms’ length bodies are delivering more efficient estates and operations by reducing greenhouse gas emissions from buildings and travel, creating less waste, consuming less water, and procuring more sustainably.

UK-S-16 Industrial Energy Efficiency Accelerator (IEEA)

Through the IEEA, the Carbon Trust works collaboratively with industry sectors to deliver energy savings in manufactured processes accelerating cost-effective innovation in process control and the uptake of low-carbon technologies.

UK-S-17 Climate Change Agreement

This programme exempts industries from most of the climate change levy if they meet targets for energy efficiency and/or reducing emissions.

Climate Change Agreements (CCAs) are voluntary agreements that allow eligible energy-intensive sectors to receive up to 90% reduction in the Climate Change Levy if they sign up to stretching energy efficiency targets agreed with government. A total of 53 industrial sectors across more than 9,000 sites have signed up to targets. Targets apply to participating sectors from 2013 to 2020, with the scheme running until 2023. The estimated carbon and energy savings of the CCA scheme is set out in the 2 April 2013 press release. The government has introduced a 100% exemption from CCL for energy used in certain energy-intensive (metallurgical and mineralogical) industrial processes. All businesses

that hold a CCA and carry out these processes can continue to participate in the scheme. These businesses can claim 100% relief for those industrial processes now exempt from CCL and, where applicable, CCA discount on all other industrial processes.

UK-S-18 Carbon Trust and Energy Saving Trust

This is a not-for-profit organisation that encourages businesses and the public sector to reduce their energy consumption, promote energy efficiency and reduce emissions. They provide some loans to help achieve this.

UK-S-10 VIBES Award Scheme (Vision In Business for the Environment in Scotland) – Scottish

Held each year, the VIBES awards recognise and showcase best practise in improving or reducing impact on the environment. It aims to encourage the efficient use of resources, improve environmental performance and support the wider goals of sustainable development.

UK-S-20 Learning for Change – Scotland

Learning for Change is Scotland's action plan for the second half of the UN decade of education for sustainable development. This document set out actions to educate people about energy efficiency and other sustainable behaviours. It covers the following topics:

- The United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (UNDESD)
- Scotland's Response
- How has this Action Plan been developed?
- What is Sustainable Development?
- What is Education for Sustainable Development?
- What are the Benefits of ESD?

UK-S-21 Campaigns of social marketing – Scotland

The Scottish Government undertake some campaigns which aim to deliver a Greener Scotland. For example: Go Greener (energy efficiency, transport); Zero Waste (recycling); Food (eat fresh and seasonal).

UK-S-22 RD&D Policies (UK Renewable Energy Strategy)

This strategy commits about GBP 50 million (approx. €62.5 million) until 2015 aimed at developing innovation in areas like offshore wind, marine energy, waste and biomass.

Energy research activity in the UK is framed by the UK 's energy strategy goals, set out in the 2003 Energy White Paper "Our energy future - creating a low carbon economy". These are to: put the UK on a path to cutting CO₂ emissions by

60% by 2050; maintain reliability of energy supplies; ensure that every home is adequately and affordably heated; and raise the rate of sustainable economic growth and improve productivity through competitive markets.

Because of their long-term nature, these goals must be underpinned by RD&D and technological innovation. Traditional science and engineering RD&D has a key role to play, but the policy emphasis on environmental progress, social objectives and the role of markets underlines the need for a "whole systems" perspective, with the inclusion and integration of relevant social, economic and environmental research.

UK-S-23 Green Deal Finance Company

This is a Not-for-profit organisation that has secured investment from 16 industry participants. This ensures finance is available to Green Deal Providers when they need it.

I-3. Republic of Poland

I-3.1. Normative policy instruments, Poland (P-N)

P-N-01 Energy Law Act

The Energy Law Act of 10 April of 1997 (with later amendments) established the basis for third party access, independent electricity and gas system, independent power producers, renewable energy sources, least cost planning, integrated resource planning, the energy regulatory authority, high efficiency heat and power production, demand side management and energy efficiency labels.

P-N-02 Quota System

Plant operators producing electricity using renewable energy sources receive 1 Green Certificate (certificate of origin) per 1 MWh of generated electricity. The Energy Law obliges some industrial customers, electricity generators, electricity suppliers, end-users who are members of the commodity exchange, commodity brokerage houses or brokerage houses to meet a certain quota of green certificates (certificates of origin) (art. 9a par. 1 no. 1 Energy Law). As an alternative, the companies may pay a fee (art. 9a par. 1 no. 2 Energy Law). Satisfying neither of these obligations carries a penalty (art. 56 par. 1 no. 1a) Energy Law). Electricity producers may also sell their electricity on the market or offer it to an electricity supplier at last year's market price. Operators of micro-installations (installations using renewable energy sources with a capacity up to 40 kW connected to the grid of max 110 kV voltage (art. 3 No. 20b Energy Law)), who decide to sell their generated electricity to an electricity supplier receive only 80% of last year's market price (art. 9v Energy Law).

P-N-03 Energy Performance of Buildings (Directive 2002/91/EC) (EU countries)

The Directive covers four main elements: Establishment of a methodology for calculating the integrated energy performance of buildings; Application of minimum standards to new and certain existing buildings; Certification schemes based on the standards; Specific inspection and assessment of boilers and heating/cooling installations.

P-N-04 Requirements for new and modernised buildings

The newest regulation on buildings codes imposes obligations to fulfil the requirements for different building components and simultaneously the requirements for maximum values of specific non-primary energy use for heating, cooling and electricity consumption for lighting.

I-3.2. Mandatory informative policy instruments, Poland (P-MI)

P-MI-01 National Renewable Energy Action Plan (NREAP) of Poland

The Effort Sharing Decision establishes binding annual greenhouse gas emission targets for EU Member States for the period 2013–2020. These targets concern emissions from most sectors not included in the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), such as transport (except aviation), buildings, agriculture and waste. The national emission target for Poland under the Effort Sharing Decision is a maximum 14% increase in greenhouse gas emissions in 2020 compared to the 2005 level.

P-MI-02 Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2011)

National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAP) under the Energy Services Directive (2006/32/EC).

P-MI-03 Certification scheme for RES installations

The certification scheme for solar thermal installations certifies that installations comply with the PN – EN 12975-1 standard. Installations must comply with the requirements specified in the "Regulation on Solar Thermal Systems and Components - Solar Collectors - Part 1: General Requirements" or possess a "Solar Keymark" certificate (9 par. 2 Priority Programme RES Solar). Certification is a precondition for receiving subsidies for the purchase and installation of solar thermal installations granted by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (see Subsidy from the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management - Solar). Installations must meet the technical and quality standards specified in the Priority Programme RES Solar (9 par. 2 Priority Programme RES Solar). The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management recognises and uses harmonised European

standards. Certification of any of these standards must be renewed after 5 years. Certificates will be accepted only if they were issued no more than 5 years prior to the date of loan application (9 par. 2 Priority Programme RES Solar).

I-3.3. Fiscal policy instruments, Poland (P-F)

P-F-01 Thermal Modernisation Fund

According to regulation, the investor (building owners or administrators) is supported by the state by a premium, which can cover up to 20% of a credit loan taken out for investment in improving the thermal efficiency of buildings.

P-F-02 Promotion of solar collectors in households sector (RES - Solar)

Subsidy program for solar collectors which is implemented as a Priority Programme "Renewable Energy Sources" of the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (NFOSiGW). It offers financial support for the purchase and installation of solar collectors.

P-F-03 Offer for households by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (include RES-Solar and Prosumer)

In 2011, the offer for households (through local government units) was extended to include grants and loans for home wastewater treatment plants and connecting buildings to collective sewerage systems. In cooperation with banks, the NFOSiGW launched in 2013 a programme of co-financing loans for construction or purchase of energy-efficient buildings. Also in 2013 the "Prosumer" programme will be available – a co-financing facility for purchase and installation of renewable energy microinstallations.

P-F-04 Housing Subsidy Programme - This programme is run by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (NFOSiGW)

The programme's budget is around €75m to support the use of renewables in the housing sector with subsidies running from the beginning of 2013 till the end of 2018. It is anticipated to reach nearly 12,000 houses and apartments. Owners receive grants to renovate or build new homes, and the amount of the grant is dependent on the targeted level of annual energy use. A grant of PLN 50,000 (approx. €12,000) is given for a target of 15 kWh/m², and a grant of PLN 30,000 (approx. €7,200) is given for a target of 40 kWh/m². There is additional provision for smaller grants targeted at flat owners: PLN 16,000 (approx. €3,800) for a target of 15 kWh/m² and PLN 11,000 (approx. €2,600) for a target of 40 kWh/m². The regional branch offices of NFOSiGW have additional incentive schemes for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and the public sector. NFOSiGW provides loans covering up to 75% of the total investment and subsidising 15% of the installation costs. The maximum amount that could be

received through the program is PLN 50m (approx. €12m) and is provided for a maximum repayment time of 10 years. The loans are mainly available to large installations of solar systems.

P-F-05 Subsidy (National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management - Prosumer)

The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (NFOSiGW) grants low interest loans together with subsidies to support the purchase and installation of small and micro-RES installations for the needs of residential single-family or multi-family houses (1, 7.5 Priority Programme Prosumer). There are two different schemes – one is designed for local government units or their compounds and is governed by the NFOSiGW, the other one addresses private persons, homeowner associations and housing cooperatives and is governed by a bank. The duration of the scheme is 2014-2020

P-F-06 Green Investment Scheme

Under Article 17 of the Kyoto Protocol, countries may participate in international emissions trading of their Assigned Amount Units (AAUs). Within this framework, Poland can use approximately 500 Mt of CO₂ equivalent. The Polish Green Investment Scheme (GIS) guarantees the "greening" of financial resources generated from the sale of AAUs, creating an institutional structure to ensure the effective management of the scheme and that funds are used for purposes directly or indirectly related to climate protection.

Part 5 of the Green Investment Scheme (Energy Management in Buildings of Selected Public Sector Entities) supports thermo-modernisation of public buildings of selected public sector entities. The maximum permissible limit of funding is up to 100% of eligible costs.

P-F-07 Energy Efficient House

This programme offers grants to people who build new or renovate their old homes and whose retrofitted houses use no more than 15kWh/m² or 40kWh/m² (depending on the grant amount) annually from external sources of heating and electricity.

P-F-08 Energy Efficient Public Buildings LEMUR

The aim is to avoid CO₂ emissions in relation to the design and construction of new energy efficient public buildings by offering grants and loans. Funding is in the form of grants of up to 30, 50 or 70% of the design, depending on the energy efficiency class of the proposed building and in the form of a loan of up to 1000 PLN per 1 m² of built floor area in rooms with controlled temperature air in the

building. This loan is granted for a period of up to 15 years with a one-year grace period on principal repayment, calculated from the date of completion of the task, which will generate savings that can be used to meet repayment obligations. The interest rate will likely be 3M WIBOR plus 0.5 basis points, but not less than 4.5%. Formal requirement for reimbursement of expenditure on the project documentation will obtain a final building permit, subject to the start of construction for a period not longer than two years after the effective date of this decision and the submission of applications for the job more than 1 million PLN. The loan may be remitted respectively 70%, 50% or 30% according to the parameters achieved efficiency. Redemption takes place after three years from the end of the Investment and obtaining an occupancy permit, and its height will depend on the resulting average reduction in energy demand and primary utility.

P-F-09 Eco Fund

The EcoFund was created in 1992 by the Ministry of Finance through the conversion of part of the Polish debt for an environmental protection fund. It was the forerunner of NFOSiGW and provides an attractive institution to subsidise renewable installations in Poland. By the end of 2007 the EcoFund had granted over 22,000 m² of solar thermal collectors and a further 18,500 m² were set to be subsidised between 2008 and 2009.

P-F-10 Subsidy (National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management - Solar)

The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management grants subsidies to cover parts of a loan taken out to purchase and install solar collectors (7.1 Priority Programme RES Solar). The duration of the scheme is 2010-2015 (4 No. 1 Priority Programme RES Solar). The collectors must be installed by an expert who has been certified according to the requirements specified in Appendix II of the Priority Programme RES Solar.

P-F-11 Subsidy (Thermo-modernisation grants)

The thermo-modernisation grant scheme supports building renovations, which increase energy efficiency or the use of renewable energy sources for heating purposes. Lenders may receive grants to pay off part of the loan taken out to implement such measures. Eligible measures shall reduce a building's annual energy demand, annual energy losses or annual costs of heat production or replace existing heat generation plants with renewable or high-efficiency CHP plants (art. 3 par. 4 Act on Thermo-Modernisation).

P-F-12 Provincial Funds for Environmental Protection and Water Management (WFOŚiGW)

These were designed to handle smaller projects of less than PLN 10m (approx. €2.4m). Provincial Funds for Environmental Protection and Water Management (WFOŚiGW) provide grants to companies, institutions and individuals engaged in business activities. Grants are intended for purchase and installation of solar thermal systems, heat pumps, photovoltaic solar panels, biomass boilers and heat recovery devices. The grant amount is up to 40% of the total cost of the project.

P-F-13 Regional Operational Programmes (ROP) of the EU

Even more money will be distributed through ROP: the EC Baltic Renewable Energy Centre states that solar collector buyers will receive additional PLN 240m to 270m (approx. €57m to €65m) from these sources alone. The EU offers subsidies of up to 85% of installation costs.

P-F-14 Poland Sustainable Energy Financing Facility (PolSEFF)

PolSEFF is a € 180 million credit line to help small and medium sized businesses in Poland invest in new, sustainable energy technologies. It is provided by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD). PolSEFF is available for three major types of investment: Simple investments based on a list of eligible materials and equipment (LEME); Large scale energy efficiency, renewable energy and building sector projects; Investments by Suppliers.

P-F-15 Energy loan for energy saved (energopozyczka)

The Industrial Development Agency has set up a loan fund "Energy loan for energy saved" for financing projects improving energy efficiency. The loan may apply to micro, small and medium sized businesses.

P-F-16 Loans from the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management

The National Fund awards low-interest loans to environmentally sustainable projects. Falling under the Air Protection category are: project that improve the processing of energy production, processing, distribution and use; those that increase the production of energy from renewable sources; and those that prevent emissions from fuel combustion.

P-F-17 Renewable Energy Tax Excise

According to the Excise Duty Act, electricity produced from renewable energy sources is exempt from excise duty. The exemption is granted on the basis of

certificates of origin that certify electricity produced from renewable sources (in accordance with the Energy Law Act).

P-F-18 Loan (National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management - Stork)

The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management grants low interests loans to support the purchase and installation of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) installations. The duration of the scheme is 2014-2020. The support may not be combined with other support schemes from the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management. All Renewable Energy Systems except for geothermal energy are eligible.

P-F-19 Tax Regulation Mechanism

In Poland, a tax is levied on the sale of electricity to end-users and their consumption (art. 9 Tax Act). Electricity from renewable sources is exempt from consumption tax (art. 30 par. 1 Tax Act).

I-3.4. Market based policy instruments, Poland (P-MB)

P-MB-01 Obligation for Power Purchase from Renewable Sources (system of green certificates) and RES-Regulation

In order to promote the utilisation of renewable energy sources for energy production, Poland introduced a support system for generating electricity from renewable energy sources. The Regulation has introduced an obligation on electricity suppliers to have a certain RES share in their total volume of electricity sales. (Related to Energy Law Act)

I-3.5. Support policy instruments, Poland

P-S-01 Infrastructure and Environment Operations Programme and the Regional Operations Programme

This provides nationwide financial support from a public fund. It ensures financial support for project relating to the energy efficiency modernisation of public buildings and or exchanging the equipment in these buildings for energy saving equipment.

P-S-02 Polish Energy Policy until 2030

On 10 November 2009, the council of Ministers adopted the strategy document Polish Energy Policy until 2030. This document outlines a long-term strategy for the entire Polish energy sector, including fuel and energy demand forecasts. It also outlines a comprehensive programme of policies and measures to be implemented by 2012.

P-S-03 KAWKA Programme

This aims at reducing the impact of human exposure to air pollutants in areas where these significantly exceed their target concentration levels, and for which air protection programs have been developed. The program objective will be achieved by reducing emissions, in particular particulate matter PM 2.5, PM 10, and CO₂ emissions.

P-S-04 Regional Sustainable Energy Action Plan, Pomerania - Pomorskie voivodeship (Pomeranian region)

These plans should serve as examples of good practice and encourage local governments to create their own action plans to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

P-S-05 Programme "Energy Savings and Renewable Energy Sources Promotion" (under the EEA Financial Mechanism and Norwegian Financial Mechanism)

The measure concerns the support of investments reducing energy consumption in buildings and utilisation of renewable energy sources.

I-4. Energy Efficiency Building Policies Characterisation - IT

I-4.1. Normative policy instruments, Italy (I-N)

I-N-01 Italian Building Codes / Standards / Regulations

In Italy, the Regions are subdivided into Provinces, and these into municipalities (comuni). Each of these Comuni implements their own building regulations, with their own sustainable building codes (norme per l'edilizia sostenibile), but based on Regional guidelines. Certain elements are integrated from national laws and decrees, but in principle there is no national system of building regulations. The appropriate local authority building codes for this flagship project is Piedmont.

I-N-02 Implementation of the EPBD in Italy

EPBD RECAST (EU 2012) ratified the 4th July 2014

I-N-03 Exemplary role of public authorities in accordance with Art. 13 Abs, 5 RES Directive

In general, all new buildings and buildings undergoing major refurbishment must take the use of integrated RES into consideration (Art. 11, c. 1 DL 28/11). The values below apply to all buildings, for public buildings, such obligations are increased by 10% (Art. 6, Annex 3, DL 28/11). RES-H plants must guarantee: 50% coverage of the foreseen consumption of warm sanitary water; and coverage of the following percentages of the cumulative foreseen consumption of warm sanitary water, heating and cooling. 20 % if the request of the relevant building permit occurs between 31/05/2012 and 31/12/2012; 35 % if the request of the relevant building permit occurs between 01/01/2014 and 31/12/2016; 50 % if

the request of the relevant building permit occurs after 01/01/2017 (Art. 1, Annex 3, DL 28/11)

I-N-04 Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS)

This directive constitutes an important guideline for the energy performance of buildings and addresses mandatory minimum requirements for the primary energy demand of new houses.

I-N-05 Regional Measures for Energy Efficiency: Piedmont Outdoor Lighting

Piedmonts March 2000 code specified the correct orientation of buildings external lighting systems - to be from above, aside from monuments - and street lighting. The code further established technical standards for efficiency, distance and light flow regulation to reduce nocturnal pollution and improve energy efficiency. Provinces verify the rational use of energy for external artificial lighting in town centres and other public and private spaces.

I-4.2. Mandatory informative policy instruments, Italy

I-MI-01 Certification Programmes for RES installations (Certification of RES installations)

After installing the plant, the installer must provide the owner of the building with a declaration certifying compliance with the legislation in force related to the realisation and the installation of the specific plant and with the standards of the Italian National Unification Body (UNI) and of the Italian Electrotechnical Committee (CEI) (Art. 6, c. 1, DM 37/08).

I-MI-02 EPBD Energy Performance Building Directive (Energy Performance Certificate)

Applied to all new buildings, residential or commercial, except religious ones. All new buildings are obliged to satisfy at least 50% of hot water demand by means of solar generation. This measure also requires that all buildings bought, sold or leased, residential or commercial will require an energy performance certificate as of 25 July 2009.

I-MI-03 Guidelines for Energy Certification Scheme of buildings

In the framework of the on-going transposition of the European Directive EPBD 2002/91/CE, the decree implements the energy performance certificate provisions of Directive in all Regions through a homogeneous framework, with a package of instruments to harmonise government and regional legislation. The guidelines apply to Regions that have not as yet implemented provisions under the EPBD for building certification and applies until any regional legislation takes effect. Regions will need to harmonise their implementation of the Directive with the guidelines.

I-MI-04 Implementation Regulation: calculation methodology of building energy performance

It establishes the general measures, calculation methodology for heating and cooling systems, and also for artificial lighting of non-residential buildings, with the goal of ensuring the homogeneous and operative application of energy efficiency policy at a national level.

I-MI-05 Feed-in tariff I (tariffa onnicomprensiva)

All plants except for PV plants with an installed power between 1kW and 1 MW are entitled to choose this feed-in tariff in alternative to the premium tariff (Art. 7, c. 4 DM 06/07/12). Depending on their size, plants may access this scheme directly or after undergoing listing in a register with capacity limits set per year.

I-MI-06 Feed-in tariff II (Ritiro dedicato)

Ritiro Dedicato is the regulation of the sale of electricity in Italy rather than a "classical" feed-in tariff. GSE (Gestore Servizi Energetici) manages the sale on behalf of the producers, who thus need not sell their energy on the free market in person. For this reason, GSE can be considered a mediator between the producers and the market. This system enables renewable energy to access the market indirectly and more easily. Producers up to certain capacities (100kW for PV and 500kW for Hydro if they make use of support schemes, 1 MW for all sources if they do not make use of support schemes) may choose between the minimum tariff (prezzo minimo garantito) determined by the energy authority and the market prices (Art. 7 AEEG 280/07 in connection with Art. 4 AEEG 34/05). Minimal prices are calculated and updated as established by the formulas in Art. 7 AEEG 280/07 and Table 1 of AEEG 280/07. Ritiro dedicato is not eligible for plants that benefit from the Premium Tariff II, the Tendering scheme or the Tariffa Omnicomprensiva (Art. 7, c. 7 DM 06/07/12)

I-MI-07 Premium Tariff I

All plants except for PV plants are eligible for receiving this premium tariff. Plants with an installed power between 1kW and 1 MW are entitled to choose a feed-in tariff (tariffa onnicomprensiva) in alternative to the premium tariff (Art. 7, c. 4 DM 06/07/12). This system is alternative to any other public incentive, to the ritiro dedicato and to the Scambio sul Posto (Art. 7, 23 and 29 DM 06/07/12)

I-MI-08 Premium tariff II (Conto energia per il solare termodinamico)

In this premium tariff scheme, plants are granted a tariff, which depends on the percentage of electricity actually produced from solar energy (in case of hybrid installations, i.e. plants that pair CSP with another source for electricity production).

I-MI-09 *New Feed-in premium for renewable energy sources other than photovoltaic (Incentives as per Ministerial Decree of 6 Jul. 2012)*

The Decree establishes new procedures for supporting electricity generation by RES-E plants (other than photovoltaic ones) with a capacity of at least 1 kW. The incentives covered by the Decree apply to new, totally rebuilt, reactivated, repowered/upgraded or renovated plants which will be commissioned on or after 1 January 2013.

I-MI-10 *All-inclusive feed-in tariff (To) (part of Incentives as per MD of 6 Jul. 2012)*

The all-inclusive feed-in tariff (tariffa onnicomprensiva) is a national scheme applicable to RES-E plants (excluding solar ones), which have a nominal real power of less than 1 MW. The tariff is granted over a period of 15 years, during which its rate remains fixed and based on the amount of electricity fed into the grid, for all plants commissioned by 31 December 2012.

I-4.3. Market based policy instruments, Italy (I-MB)

I-MB-01 *Kyoto Fund*

SMEs, PAs or individuals can benefit from a 0.5% interest rate financial tool to realise their energy efficiency projects (including building sector), distributed generation (tri-generation in particular), or small renewable energy production plants. The funding is 200M€ per year for the period 2012-2014.

I-MB-02 *Support of RES-H infrastructure II (Fondo Kyoto)*

The Kyoto Fund has a wide scope, and within this fund RES-H infrastructure is also supported. The fund has a total amount of € 600 million, broken down in three equal parts for three years: 2012, 2013, 2014 (Art. 1, c. 1113, l. 296/06 in connection with Art. 1, c. 1-3, C 16/02/2012).

I-MB-03 *Net-Metering (scambio sul posto)*

In Italy, RES-E producers can make use of net-metering ("Scambio Sul Posto") if their plant's capacity is 20 kW to 200 kW (lower than 20 kW if commissioned before 31 December 2007) This possibility may be taken instead of the tariffa onnicomprensiva or the sale of electricity in the free market or in the market governed by "Ritiro Dedicato, or the Premium Tariff I or the Tendering Scheme. The principle of Scambio sul Posto is not based on direct payments but on the balance of the energy fed in and consumed (Art. 1, 2 570/2012/R/efr). Scambio sul posto in accordance with 570/2012/R/efr differs from traditional net metering, as the plant operator pays the supplier for the electricity consumed, while GSE (Gestore Servizi Energetici) gives credit for the electricity fed in. This method can lead to a surplus on behalf of the plant operator (Art. 1 par. 1 a 570/2012/R/efr). The balance is calculated once a year (Art. 8 par. 2

570/2012/R/efr). Precisely, the owner of such plants will receive a compensation equal to the difference between the value of electricity exported to the grid (e.g. for PV installations the energy fed in during daytime) and the value of the electricity consumed in a different period. If more energy is fed in than is consumed, this positive balance can compensate for a possible negative balance in the following years (Art. 6 par. 7 570/2012/R/efr). Generators who feed in more electricity than they consume do not receive any payment under the net metering scheme. If they feed in less than they consume, the difference is subject to a payment. Plant operators receive credit for electricity produced but not consumed. This credit will be available for an unlimited period of time (Art. 6 par. 7 570/2012/R/efr).

I-MB-04 Tenders

All plants beyond a certain capacity except for PV plants are eligible for receiving incentives in the form of a premium tariff after undergoing a tendering process. This system is alternative to any other public incentive, to the Ritiro Dedicato and to the Scambio sul Posto (Art. 7, 23 and 29 DM 06/07/12)

I-MB-05 Heating and Cooling Funding Schemes & Statutory Provisions Listing

Means of Support - Loan (Fondo Kyoto), Price Based Mechanisms (Conto Termico) Tax Regulation Mechanism (Tax Deduction). Summary of Schemes - 1) Price-based scheme. This scheme provides an incentive for small RES-H sources. The eligibility depends on the source and the type of installation.2) Loan. The loan has a life-span of three years (2012 – 2013 – 2014) and a total amount of € 600 million. It supports biomass, biogas, geothermal and solar thermal plants, 3) Tax regulation scheme. This scheme allows for a 55 % tax deduction (“detrazione”) for expenses related to refurbishment of existing buildings and / or energetic requalification of buildings and / or installation of RES-H technologies

I-MB-06 Energy Efficiency Certificates (EEC or Italian acronym TEE), known as white certificates system

They are tradable instruments giving proof of the achievement of end-use energy savings through energy efficiency improvements initiatives and projects. Each electricity and gas distributor with more than 50,000 final users has to achieve a target of energy savings, and they may fulfil their obligation either by implementing energy efficient projects that benefit their consumers, which will earn them white certificates, or by buying white certificates from other parties in the Energy Efficiency Certificates Market that is organised by GME. Parties eligible to submit projects for accruing white certificates are: i) electricity and gas

distributors with more than 50,000 final customers (“obliged parties”) and their controlled companies; ii) non-obliged distributors; iii) companies operating in the sector of energy services (ESCOs); and iv) companies or organisations having an energy manager or an ISO 50001-certified energy management system in place.

I-MB-07 White Certificates Standards (Italy and other EU countries)

Standards certifying that a certain reduction of energy consumption has been attained. Tied to Energy Efficiency Certificates.

I-MB-08 Green Certificates (GCs)

Green Certificates (GCs) are tradable instruments that GSE grants to qualified renewable-energy power plants (IAFR qualification) that have been commissioned before 31 December 2012 as per Legislative Decree 28/2011.

I-4.4. Fiscal policy instruments, Italy (I-F)

I-F-01 55% Tax Rebate Scheme

The 55% tax rebate scheme provides tax credits to households for comprehensive or single retrofit energy efficiency measures, such as thermal insulation, installation of solar panels, replacement of heating and air-conditioning systems or comprehensive refurbishments. The total deductible amount is then distributed over a period of ten years. Tax credit can cover 55% of the energy-related cost, but cannot exceed a maximum value that is determined by the type of measure taken. Tax credits are reimbursed over 10 years, beginning with the completion of work.

The tax credit is 65% in 10 years for retrofit with relevant energy efficiency measures realised in 2014, reduced to 50% in 2015.

I-F-02 Fiscal incentives for energy savings in the household sector: Ecobonus 2014 and tax deduction for renovations and appliances

A series of tax benefits for taxpayers who have on-going construction projects have been introduced, aiming to revitalise a sector heavily in crisis.

The tax credit is 55% in 10 years for building refurbishment (even if without energy efficiency measures)

I-F-03 Tax regulation mechanisms I (Reduction in value-added tax)

Since 1993, Italy has promoted the generation of electricity from wind and solar energy through a reduction of 10 % on the value-added tax (l'aliquota agevolata del 10 per cento) for deliveries and services related to investments in wind power plants and solar energy installations and investments in grids that distribute this electricity.

I-F-04 Tax regulation mechanisms II (Reduction in real estate tax)

The Budget Act of 2008 gives municipalities the opportunity to grant a reduction in real estate tax (imposta municipale propria, IMU) to buildings equipped with renewable energy installations. The amount of IMU depends on the value of the property and differs from municipality to municipality.

I-F-05 Special fund to support the implementation of energy efficiency target

Decree-Law of 25 March 2010, No 40, established a special fund for the implementation of objectives related to energy efficiency, environmental protection and workplace safety. The decree specifies the activities towards which funding is dedicated. For energy efficiency, this fund provides incentives for the following: high efficient appliances, replacing motorcycles with class Euro 0 or Euro 1 with motorcycles class Euro 3, purchase of new buildings with class A or B - according to Italian Energy Certification Scheme -, purchase and installation of inverters, high efficiency motors, uninterruptible power sources (UPS) and capacitors, purchase of newer and more efficient farm machinery and machinery for construction and boats.

I-F-06 Renewable Energy for Heating and Cooling Support Scheme (Conto Termico)

This scheme supports small-scale projects of energy efficiency improvement and production of thermal energy from renewables. Grants are given for projects in the following areas: energy efficiency improvements in existing envelopes; replacement of existing systems for winter heating with more efficient ones; replacement and, in some cases, construction of new renewable-energy systems. It also provides incentives for energy auditing and energy certification associated with the above projects.

I-4.5. Support policy instruments, Italy (I-S)

I-S-01 Italy's National Energy Strategy: For a more competitive and sustainable energy - March 2013

4 main goals of the National Energy Strategy are: Significantly reduce the energy cost gap; Achieve and exceed the environmental and decarbonisation targets; Continue to improve our security supply; Foster sustainable economic growth.

I-S-02 Training programmes for installers

Art. 15 of DL 28/11, in connection with DM 37/08, indicates that training programmes for obtaining the professional qualification of installer will have to be set up by regional authorities. Specific indications on the courses, such as mandatory examination and training period, are given in Annex 4 DL 28/11. Such courses are one of the possible ways of obtaining a professional qualification, the other ones being a related university diploma, a technical institute diploma with

two years of experience afterwards, a period of four years in a related company with a title validating the acquired skills, a period of three years as specialised installer working for a qualified company (Art. 4, c. 1, ll. a-d DL 37/08)

I-S-03 *Heating and Cooling Policies & Statutory Provisions Listing*

In Italy training programmes for installers are regulated at central level but set up and managed at regional level. Each installer, after having installed a plant on any building, is required by law to release a certificate of compliance with a set of standards outlined in DM 37/08. All new buildings and all buildings undergoing major refurbishment are obliged to integrate RES-E and RES-H. There are different obligations depending on the building type and size, and for public buildings the obligations are increased by 10%. A guarantee fund supporting the development of district heating networks is in place within the “Cassa conguaglio” for the electricity sector. An additional fee of € 0.05/Sm³ (Sm³ is a quantity measurement unit at specified pressure and temperature levels) is applied to the consumption of natural gas. The “Fondo Kyoto” allows loans at a subsidised rate for district heating infrastructure under certain conditions.

I-S-04 *Information on Supports and Policies with regards to renewables in EU*

The website outlines the information for each country and also has a compare function where you can select specific countries, and their policies or supports, etc. and compare them

I-S-05 *Environmental Action Strategy for Sustainable Development in Italy*

Ministry for the Environment and Territory Policy Document

I-S-06 *Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan - July 2011*

National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAP) under the Energy Services Directive (2006/32/EC)

I-S-07 *Energy efficiency target declared by Italy under the EU directive (2012/27/EU)*

Multi-sectoral policy. Target reports available online from the International Energy Agency website.

I-S-08 *RES-E ("IAFR") qualification of plants*

The qualification of plants as plants using renewable energy sources ("IAFR" - RES-E) is a pre-requisite to obtain green certificates or the all-inclusive feed-in tariff.